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Project Summary

European musical heritage is a dynamic historical flow of experiences, leaving heterogeneous traces that are difficult to capture, connect, access, interpret, and valorise. Computing technologies have the potential to shed a light on this wealth of resources by extracting, materialising and linking new knowledge from heterogeneous sources, hence revealing facts and experiences from hidden voices of the past. Polifonia makes this happen by building novel ways of inspecting, representing, and interacting with digital content. Memory institutions, scholars, and citizens will be able to navigate, explore, and discover multiple perspectives and stories about European Musical Heritage.

Polifonia focuses on European Musical Heritage, intended as musical contents and artefacts - or music objects - (tunes, scores, melodies, notations, etc.) along with relevant knowledge about them such as: their links to tangible objects (theatres, conservatoires, churches, etc.), their cultural and historical contexts, opinions and stories told by people having diverse social and artistic roles (scholars, writers, students, intellectuals, musicians, politicians, journalists, etc), and facts expressed in different styles and disciplines (memoire, reportage, news, biographies, reviews), different languages (English, Italian, French, Spanish, and German), and across centuries.

The overall goal of the project is to realise an ecosystem of computational methods and tools supporting discovery, extraction, encoding, interlinking, classification, exploration of, and access to, musical heritage knowledge on the Web. An equally important objective is to demonstrate that these tools improve the state of the art of Social Science and Humanities (SSH) methodologies. Hence their development is guided by, and continuously intertwined with, experiments and validations performed in real-world settings, identified by musical heritage stakeholders (both belonging to the Consortium and external supporters) such as cultural institutes and collection owners, historians of music, anthropologists and ethnomusicologists, linguists, etc.

Executive Summary

Deliverable D4.7, "Evaluation of Plurilingual Corpora and Knowledge Exaction Methods", provides a final evaluation of Knowledge Extraction (KE) methods and tools developed within Work Package 4 (WP4).

Extracting knowledge from texts, particularly in historical contexts, remains a complex endeavour. The Polifonia project's focus on Musical Heritage (MH) preservation adds unique challenges to analyzing textual documents. In fact, the Polifonia Textual Corpus¹ [1] comprises historical documents, which cannot fully benefit from the most recent advancements in Natural Language Processing (NLP). Transformer architectures [2] like BERT [3] or Large Language Models (LLM) like ChatGPT [4] have been primarily trained and evaluated on contemporary and clean documents. As a consequence, peculiar linguistic variations related to historical documents make it problematic for pre-trained language models to encode words or recognize syntactic structures as effectively as for contemporary documents. Also, when dealing with NLP models, it is important to consider not only linguistic variations but also the impact of Optical Character Recognition (OCR) errors. These errors can lead to unintended behaviour in LLMs, which are typically trained on clean text.

Moreover, a challenge in reusing current NLP models on historical documents lies in the different distribution of named entities between historical and contemporary texts. In fact, advanced NLP techniques for Entity Linking (EL), namely the process of connecting mentions in a text to their corresponding entries in a knowledge base like Wikipedia, have limitations. These models may produce inconsistent associations due to the fact that their training sets contain mostly contemporary documents [5] or due to the lack of representation of minor historical entities in the reference knowledge base. Consequently, a named entity mention of an XVIII-century person occurring in a document published in XVIII century might be linked to a XX-century character, leading to erroneous results.

Furthermore, the performance of current NLP models on open-domain Question Answering (QA) tasks is not satisfactory when the questions are centred around named entities that are less frequent in the models' training sets, such as the ones occurring in historical texts. LLMs, including the largely popular conversational agent chatGPT [6], demonstrate a stronger tendency to hallucinate or to reply incorrectly when prompted with factual questions eliciting long-tail knowledge on less popular entities. When dealing with such types of questions, augmenting the prompt sent as input to LLMs with retrieved evidence appears to improve performance [7].

Given these issues, our deliverable focuses on evaluating the enhancements that we brought to our KE pipeline (Polifonia Knowledge Extractor²) to make it more suitable for accurately processing historical texts:

- Release of an advanced historical named entities recognition, classification and linking benchmark in English language;
- Introduction and evaluation of a novel EL model;
- Introduction of an adaptation of a widely utilised neural EL model that filters out implausible candidates based on time and type information from Wikidata;
- Introduction of a factual QA benchmark focused on historical, long-tail named entities;
- Presentation of a methodology for evaluating and comparing KE models along with the discussion of the results of its application.

The evaluation methods and tools designed and tested in this deliverable contribute to the general goal of WP4: making musical heritage knowledge available through reliable knowledge graphs that can be easily queried.

¹<https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/corpus/>

²<https://github.com/polifonia-project/Polifonia-Knowledge-Extractor>

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1. General Introduction

In this final report, we outline the advances made under Polifonia's WP4 (Work Package 4). The primary objective of WP4 is to equip the project and its pilots with effective techniques and instruments for extracting Musical Heritage (MH) insights from textual sources. In the course of the project, we initially devoted our efforts to constructing and assessing a multilingual text collection for MH (Task 4.1), referred to as the Polifonia Textual Corpus [1]. This extensive collection of documents is the basis from which we started to develop methods and tools aimed at ensuring the conservation of MH knowledge and its easy querying and retrieval by the general public. In order to achieve this goal, we made available automatic tools for enriching texts and data with linguistic annotations[8], as well as a web application for querying the contents of our corpus¹.

Concerning the structuring of data into knowledge, we constructed and unveiled a comprehensive Knowledge Extraction (KE) pipeline from text, marking the debut of Polifonia Knowledge Extractor's initial iteration (Task 4.3). It enables the conversion of plain text into semantic graph structures. The first version of it, Polifonia Knowledge Extractor² (PKE), was the focus of Deliverable 4.5 and used Abstract Meaning Representation (AMR) [9] to parse sentences into semantic graphs, offering the possibility to search within large AMR graphs banks. With Deliverable 4.6, we extended PKE with an improved version of AMR2FRED³ [10], a software component that complements the PKE and allows the transformation of the AMR graphs into RDF Knowledge Graphs (KG) [11] compliant to FRED[12] knowledge patterns. The PKE and the AMR2FRED tools can be exploited jointly in the Text2AMR2FRED (API⁴ and WebApp⁵), a revised architecture of FRED's text-to-KG pipeline [13].

In the course of our work on the PKE, we identified the need for additional interventions due to the challenges encountered when handling multilingual and historical documents. While the Natural Language Processing (NLP) research effort has primarily centred around present-day language analysis, it is crucial to acknowledge that historical documents exhibit unique linguistic characteristics and stylistic variations. Furthermore, the named entities mentioned in historical documents are strongly bound to the time in which the historical document was issued. Also, historical texts can be polluted with spelling errors due to noise introduced by the image-to-text transformation obtained through Optical Character Recognition technologies. Given this context, we faced significant hurdles in reusing tools trained on text natively designed for digital printing or for publication on the web, notoriously free of the pollution introduced by OCR, featuring consistent writing styles and named entities popular in present days. The application of these tools to our historical documents resulted in numerous errors. For example, the PKE pipeline encounters difficulties in correctly linking mentions of named entities in the text of our corpus with relevant entities described in Knowledge Bases (KBs) like Wikidata.

This deliverable focuses on providing a quantifiable assessment of the improvements applied to the PKE (Task 4.4). In Chapter 2, we described the enhancements that we brought to the Entity Linking (EL) models utilized in PKE. Entity linking (EL) models commonly used for this task due to their scalability [14] exhibit a "popularity bias" issue [15]. These models tend to connect ambiguous entities' mentions with entities that frequently occur in their training sets, primarily sourced from Wikipedia [16]. Given that our documents diverge substantially from such contemporary training materials, we determined that utilizing State-of-the-Art (SotA) entity linkers would not result in optimal performance.

EL is the task of understanding who a certain named entity mentioned in a text is, with reference to real-world entities recorded in a KB [17]. It is fundamental for KE tasks that pursue the ultimate objective of empowering open-domain, factual QA systems, as they ground named entities occurring in documents to a trusted KB. EL models commonly used for this task due to their scalability [14] exhibit a "popularity bias" issue [15]. These models tend to connect

¹<https://polifonia.disi.unibo.it/corpus/>

²<https://github.com/polifonia-project/Polifonia-Knowledge-Extractor>

³<https://github.com/polifonia-project/amr2Fred>

⁴<http://framester.istc.cnr.it/txt-amr-fred/api/docs/>

⁵<https://arco.istc.cnr.it/txt-amr-fred/>

ambiguous entities' mentions with entities that frequently occur in their training sets, primarily sourced from Wikipedia [16]. Given that our documents diverge substantially from such contemporary training materials, we determined that utilizing State-of-the-Art (SotA) entity linkers would not result in optimal performance.

As a result, we devised and evaluated ELD, a custom model for historical entity linking. The game-theoretical approach to the candidates' for linking reranking phase demonstrates to be well suited for the task, beating the other baselines. Additionally, we present C-BLINK, a modified version of [14, BLINK] that improves as compared to baselines by exploiting symbolic knowledge, such as temporal and typological information contained in knowledge bases such as Wikidata, to avoid performing illogical linking to more popular, contemporary entities.

Also, we developed MHERCL, a new manually annotated benchmark for historical entity linking, which we used for evaluating the performance of our novel methods. We release its version v1.0 to expand the roster of gold-standard EL resources focused on historical data.

In Chapter 3, we report on the establishment of DYNACKNOWLEDGE v1.0, a dynamic benchmark for KE. The benchmark is designed to serve in extrinsic evaluation settings framed as Question Answering (QA) tasks. In fact, it is provided in the form of a manually crafted set of *question*, *answer*, and *provenance* tuples. The questions are factual and centred on historical named entities occurring in the Polifonia Textual Corpus. They are answerable by one or more sentences extrapolated from the Wikipedia page of the entities, recorded in the benchmark as the "provenance" information. DYNACKNOWLEDGE has been used to evaluate chatGPT's [6] ability to provide correct answers to the questions in a zero-shot prompting setting. This experiment encompassed a comparison between chatGPT's answers' correctness and PKE's capability to encode the information required to answer the question correctly. Results raise awareness of the sub-optimal performance of chatGPT when elicited to output factual knowledge about non-popular entities and the higher robustness to popularity variations of an extremely simpler KE pipeline. Also, the same subset of DYNACKNOWLEDGE has been used to evaluate chatGPT [6] in a context-augmented prompting setting. The prompt was augmented with context encoded in three different ways: 1. plain text of the provenance; 2. the AMR graph obtained from the semantic parsing of the provenance; 3. the RDF/OWL graph obtained from translating the AMR graph into a full-fledged and logically sound KG. As compared to the performance measured in the zero-context prompting setting, chatGPT's capability to correctly answer the questions improved with any of the three types of context used to augment the prompt.

1.1. Structure of the Document and Contribution

This report is structured into a general introduction and two distinct chapters. Each chapter functions independently, equivalent to standalone scientific articles, comprised of an introduction, SotA review, methodology, experimentation, analysis, and conclusion sections.

Chapter 2 focuses on the results achieved in the scope of evaluation of historical entity linking, introducing a novel benchmark and presenting new and revised models capable of processing various time-frames and languages.

Chapter 3 reports on the development of a dynamic benchmark for evaluating KE in QA tasks and presents findings from its use in assessing chatGPT's performance in zero-shot and context-augmented prompting settings.

The key contributions of this report include:

- MHERCL v1.0, an advanced benchmark for historical entity linking;
- ELD, a new entity linking model;
- C-BLINK, a modified version of BLINK that takes into account symbolic information on named entities' time and type extrapolated from trusted KBs such as Wikidata;
- DYNACKNOWLEDGE v1.0, a QA benchmark on historical, long-tail entities for extrinsically assessing KE models' performance in QA tasks;
- a method to evaluate and compare models based on latent and explicit knowledge representation.

2. Evaluation of historical entity linking

2.1. Introduction

Named Entity Recognition (NER), Named Entity Classification (NEC) and Entity Linking (EL), also referred to as Entity Disambiguation [18] are fundamental tasks in knowledge extraction and have become progressively more relevant for the analysis of historical documents due to the massive campaigns of digitisation carried out in recent years [19, 20] that aim at preserving and studying cultural heritage texts. With the NER task, mentions of named entities (such as people, locations, organisations, etc.) are identified in text and with NEC, these mentions are assigned to a pre-defined set of entity types, such as PERSON, LOCATION or ORGANISATION. Entity Linking (EL) consists of connecting named entities' mentions to the actual entity they refer to, choosing possible candidates from a reference Knowledge Base (KB), such as Wikipedia¹, DBPedia², Wikidata³. The information required to perform such a choice is commonly retrieved from the context in which mentions occur. In some cases, it is also used information from NER and NEC to restrict the list of entity candidates a mention may refer to [21]. As an example, we can refer to the mention *Jordan*, as reported in the following sentences:

- (1) *Sunni Islam is the dominant religion in Jordan.*
- (2) *Jordan joined the Bulls in 1984 as the third overall draft pick.*

The mention *Jordan* in these sentences is ambiguous and may refer to entities with different types, e.g., PERSON or LOCATION. The first sentence refers to a country in West Asia. This specific entity is indexed and described in several resources such as Wikipedia or Wikidata⁴. In the second sentence, the same mention (*Jordan*) refers to the basketball player *Michael Jordan*, in turn, indexed in a dedicated Wikipedia page and Wikidata item⁵. Looking at the two sentences in the reported examples, the surrounding context of the mentions *Jordan* makes it clear which entity in the KB *Jordan* refers to, demonstrating context's importance in EL tasks. However, other variables characterize the task of Historical Entity linking (HEL), i.e., the task of EL applied to historical texts. In fact, as reported in [19], NERC and EL on historical documents have peculiarities that make them more challenging than standard NERC and EL. This is due to several reasons, for example: (i) the noisy quality of the plain text derived through Optical Character Recognition (OCR) technologies; (ii) language variations between contemporary and non-contemporary language that affect lexical, morpho-syntactic and semantic aspects, such as spelling variation, sentence structure and naming conventions; and, (iii) the scarcity of historical documents annotated for EL and in general for Natural Language Processing (NLP) tasks. All these issues make it difficult to use state-of-the-art (SotA) models for HEL. Primarily because SotA models employ supervised learning techniques and thus are trained on contemporary data based mainly on web documents [22, 23, 15]. This problem is exacerbated by the fact that HEL may include what in standard EL training data can be considered low-frequency entities, i.e., entities that have been linked to a given mention only a few times or never.

As an example of historical entity disambiguation, we can refer to the mention *Naumann*, as seen in the sentence below, extrapolated from the issue n. 22 of the music periodical *The Quarterly Musical Magazine And Review*, dating back to 1824 and part of the Polifonia Textual Corpus¹⁵:

- (3) *The next is a solo for an alto, and a quartet from Naumann.*

¹wikipedia.org

²<https://www.dbpedia.org/>

³wikidata.org

⁴<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jordan>; <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q810>

⁵https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Michael_Jordan; <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q41421>

This mention may refer to more than 30 different named entities, as the English Wikipedia disambiguation page reports⁶, making the disambiguation very difficult. Furthermore, they are almost all historical entities, i.e., entities whose data of birth dates back more than 100 years ago. For this reason, they appear only a few times (from 0 to 3) in standard training sets [24]. However, if we look carefully at the context in which the mention appears, we can infer that the correct named entity to link should be a person related to music. Using this contextual information and reading the description of the candidates, we can restrict the candidate list on which the disambiguation has to be performed, and as a result, we have only two entities that are person named entities related to music:

1. *Johann Gottlieb Naumann (1741–1801), German composer*⁷;
2. *Ernst Naumann (1832–1910), German composer*⁸.

The desiderata for a good HEL model are thus to be able to use contextual information and to be able to encode information about named entity descriptions. These features have been implemented in SoTA models by leveraging Large Language Models (LLM) to obtain a contextualized representation of a mention and developing entity embedding models to represent entity descriptions in the same vector space of the mentions. This allows us to perform similarity queries on the entity embedding space using a contextualized representation of a mention to retrieve entity candidates for a given mention [24]. However, the entity type is not explicitly encoded in entity representations, and thus, a nearest neighbours search can give results including mixed entity types, making it impossible to filter the candidate list as we have shown above. Another variable that a HEL model must control is time. In fact, the use of temporal information allows us to filter further the list of candidates presented above, retaining only temporarily plausible entities. This information is easily accessible for historical documents and consists of the publication date of the document and the date of birth of the entities as encoded in a knowledge base. Using temporal information, we can infer that the only entity that can be linked to *Naumann* in example (3) is the first of the two proposed above since the second one has a date of birth posterior to the publication year of the periodical. This feature is not implemented in the SoTA end-to-end entity linker, and thus it is very plausible that they perform inconsistent labeling of the data, proposing contemporary entities instead of historical ones.

Driven by these observations and by practical experience, we hypothesise that the *popularity bias* in state-of-the-art (SoTA) neural entity linkers, a phenomenon investigated by [15], intensifies when applied to entities extrapolated from historical texts. Popularity bias causes popular entities, i.e. entities that are more frequent in a training set, to be preferred to less frequent entities, even if the context in which they appear is unambiguous. The cause of this heightened bias can be traced back to historical entities being less represented in popular training datasets [25]. Furthermore, in the context of historical documents, this popularity bias tends to evolve into a peculiar bias, which we term as *temporal bias*. That results in the tendency of SoTA entity linkers to favour contemporary entities over historical ones, even if other unambiguous historical entities are mentioned in the same context. Eventually, they reach lower performance when applied to historical entities found in historical texts than when applied to contemporary entities found in contemporary texts.

This phenomenon can be observed in the AMR graph produced by the text2AMR step of the [13, Text2AMR2FRED], reported in Figure 2.1. In the AMR graph, the NEs recognition and classification (NERC) performed by [26, SPRING] correctly recognises the superficial named entity's mention *Fabio Constantini*, which is erroneously linked by a SoTA entity linker [14, BLINK] to the Wikipedia page of *Claudio Constantini*⁹, a Peruvian composer born in 1983. The correct link should be to the Wikidata entity *Fabio Constantini*¹⁰, with QID Q3737659, an Italian composer born in 1575.

In this work, we design and release gold-standard resources containing NERC- and EL-annotated historical documents and models adapted for performing entity linking on historical texts by:

1. developing Entity Linking Dynamics (ELD), a new unsupervised model for HEL;
2. developing methodologies to adapt supervised SoTA model to work on historical documents, based on typo-

⁶<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Naumann>

⁷https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Johann_Gottlieb_Naumann; <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q213927>

⁸https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Ernst_Naumann; <https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q5395101>

⁹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Claudio_Constantini

¹⁰<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q3737659>

Figure 2.1: AMR graph resulting from the text2AMR parsing powered by [26, SPRING] of the sentence "Fabio Constantini flourished about the year 1630, and ultimately became maestro at the chapel of Loretto.", extrapolated from *The Quarterly Musical Magazine And Review*, n. 22 (1824), part of the *Periodicals* module of the PTC¹⁵.

logical and temporal constraints;

3. creating MHERCL (Musical Heritage Historical named Entities Recognition, Classification and Linking, a new benchmark for historical NER, NEC and EL, that is larger than previously published datasets;
4. Testing ELD and adapted EL models on HEL datasets and analyzing their results.

The release of MHERCL enriches the landscape of gold-standard resources containing NER-, NEC- and EL-annotated historical documents. ELD is an innovative model for EL that grounds its inner entity disambiguation process to the context in which entities appear, relying on relaxation labelling processes [27]. The development of the methodologies also allows for the use of supervised models in the context of historical documents.

The remainder of this section is organised as follows. In Section 2.2, we summarise the most relevant contributions regarding historical dataset collection and implemented models specifically trained on historical documents. In Section 2.3, we depict the background work that made the building of MHERCL v1.0 possible, and we describe the benchmark in terms of sampling, annotation guidelines, statistics and release details. In Section 2.5.1, we describe the implementation of ELD and in Section 2.5.2 we present the constraints used to adapt SoTA models to work on historical documents. We report our experiments' results in sub-section 2.6.

2.2. State-of-the-Art

In this section, we summarise the most significant contributions regarding historical NERC and EL datasets and the models implemented for general-purpose and historical EL, highlighting how our work positions itself with regard to the SotA.

2.2.1. Benchmarks

Recent surveys highlight how historical texts are rarely included in popular training datasets [25]. In recent years, HIPE-2020 [28, 29] and HIPE-2022 [30, 31] evaluation campaigns reviewed the most relevant datasets of historical and multilingual documents offering gold standard annotations for named entity recognition and linking. The most up-to-date output of this endeavour is the data released for the HIPE-2022 evaluation campaign, which comprises six Named Entities-annotated datasets consisting of historical newspapers and classic commentaries of 200 years time-span¹¹ in English, Finnish, French, German and Swedish. The data is sourced initially from various European cultural heritage projects, such as: (i) *NewsEye* ([32]), which provides historical newspaper articles in French, German, Finnish and Swedish dating back to 19C-20C; (ii) *SoNAR*, which includes historical newspaper articles from the Berlin State Library newspaper collections in German (19C-20C); (iii) *Le Temps*, which contains historical newspaper articles from two Swiss newspapers in French (19C-20C); (iv) *Living with Machines*, which has a dataset of historical newspaper articles from the British Library newspapers in English (18C-19C). HIPE-2022 data in English are the most relevant for our work. In HIPE-2022 data, the datasets that contain data in English are: 1. AJMC DATASET¹²; 2. TOPRES19th¹³; 3. HIPE2020¹⁴. AJMC DATASET¹² contains a specific textual genre, *Classical Commentaries*, which diverges significantly from the textual genre contained in MHERCL v1.0. Also, the tagset employed in TOPRES19th¹³ is highly specialised, focusing exclusively on toponyms.

With MHERCL v1.0, we advance the SotA by introducing a dataset of annotated English data derived from a textual source that is not represented in HIPE-2022 (historical music periodicals). This distinct dataset enriches the current repository of available annotated resources. It captures a different set of named entities and types specific to a domain, which diverges from those represented in HIPE-2022.

2.2.2. General and task-specific models

The research in the field of NERC was pioneered by [33] who proposed DIANED, a time-aware entity linking approach for diachronic corpora, which leverages KB-driven temporal information and text-driven temporal expressions. The HIPE-2022 evaluation campaign collates the most recent efforts in implementing models for NERC and EL on historical documents. The most evident tendency that can be observed is that all the systems that participated in the competition used transformer-based Pre-trained Language Models (PLM). The top ranking model on English language data, both for NER and EL, has been proposed by [34, L3i] team. Their EL model builds upon the neural technique they introduced for CLEF-HIPE-2020 [35], enhanced with a filtering process to dissect and disambiguate historical references using Wikidata, described in [36]. Leveraging data from Wikipedia, Wikidata, and DBpedia provides a comprehensive entity analysis, aiding their method in accurately disambiguating mentions in historical documents.

Given the popularity of EL and the wide range of applications that involve this task, many new models have been recently proposed. Current research revolves mainly around PLM both for encoding mentions that are then used to compare and select candidates [14] and for directly generating entity identifiers conditioned on mentions in context [37]. [14] proposed BLINK, a BERT-based entity linking model. Given an entity mention, it retrieves potential candidates by embedding this mention and performs a k-nn algorithm, searching for the most similar embedding in an entity embedding space trained on the descriptions of the entities of a KB. Each candidate is then re-ranked with a cross-encoder that concatenates the mention and entity text. A different approach, based on generative language models instead of classification architectures, was proposed in [38, GENRE]. This approach retrieves entities by generating their unique names, left to right, conditioned on the context. Such an approach directly captures relations between context and entity name and reduces the memory footprint of performing queries on large search spaces. An extension of this model was proposed in [37, mGENRE]. Also, in this case, the name of a target entity is generated in an autoregressive fashion. The only difference is that the model can be applied to different languages using a multilingual encoder and a multilingual KB.

¹¹<https://github.com/hipe-eval/HIPE-2022-data>

¹²<https://github.com/hipe-eval/HIPE-2022-data/blob/main/documentation/README-ajmc.md>

¹³<https://github.com/hipe-eval/HIPE-2022-data/blob/main/documentation/README-topres19th.md>

¹⁴<https://github.com/hipe-eval/HIPE-2022-data/blob/main/documentation/README-hipe2020.md>

In the work described in this report, we aim to advance the SotA by proposing an adapted version of BLINK (C-BLINK) in which the candidates retrieved are filtered by applying typological and temporal constraints based on the knowledge contained in a reference KB (Wikidata). Thanks to this approach, implausible entities can be removed from the roster of candidates proposed, resulting in a more accurate linking. Also, we propose ELD, a new unsupervised method for EL that disambiguates ambiguous entities using contextual information.

2.3. Background

In this section, we review the preliminary studies carried out during the Polifonia project that helped us identify the major issues that SotA supervised entity linkers present when applied to historical documents, causing poor entity linking performance. We outline the Knowledge Extraction tools that we used and report a preliminary study of the entity linking quality that we carried out by analysing the tools' output.

2.3.1. Knowledge Extraction from the Polifonia Textual Corpus

Figure 2.2: AMR graph resulting from the text2AMR parsing powered by [26, SPRING] of the sentence "A pleasing ballad, with fine melody, sung by Adelaide Phillips.", extrapolated from *Dwights Journal Of Music*, n. 12 (1868), part of the *Periodicals* module of the PTC¹⁵.

The sentences in MHERCL have been extrapolated from the Polifonia Textual Corpus (PTC)¹⁵, a multi-module, diachronic and multilingual corpus specialised on the music domain. In particular, the sentences belonged to the *Periodicals* module of the Polifonia Textual Corpus. These sentences have been processed through the Polifonia Knowledge Extractor (PKE)¹⁶ toolkit, a framework for extracting knowledge from contemporary and historical texts, which leverages as intermediate step Abstract Meaning Representation (AMR) [9], a popular formalism of natural language that represents the meaning of a sentence as a semantic graph, in which nodes represent concepts and edges represent relations among concepts. The sample is part of the *Filtered AMR Graphs Bank*¹⁷.

An example of AMR graph obtained through [26, SPRING] called via Text2AMR2FRED WebApp⁵ is reported in Figure 2.2. From this figure, it is possible to see how AMR performs both NERC and EL ((z3 person :wiki

¹⁵<https://github.com/polifonia-project/Polifonia-Corpus>

¹⁶<https://github.com/polifonia-project/Polifonia-Knowledge-Extractor>

¹⁷Available at <https://zenodo.org/record/7025779#.ZDls8OxBy3I>

"Adelaide_Phillipps":name (z4 name :op1 "Adelaide":op2 "Phillips")), the latter using Wikipedia as a KB.

2.3.2. Exploratory Study of Entity Linking Quality

Table 2.1: Table reporting statistics about the off-the-shelf quality of PKE¹⁶ framework on EL of person Named Entities in a PTC sample.

#sents	person Named Entities (Superficial mention)		person Named Entities (Wikidata QID)		person Named Entities (Date of Birth)		
	#recognised	#linked	#found	#not found	#plausible	#not plausible	#not found
2205	2262	2108	2006	102	1199	203	604

As the PKE framework, described in sub-section 2.3.1, automatically recognises named entities in its text-to-AMR parsing step, we ran a preliminary experiment to evaluate the off-the-shelf performance of the PKE text-to-AMR parser ([26, SPRING]) and its embedded entity linker, [14, BLINK]. The results are reported in Table 2.1. We focused on a sample of 2205 sentences taken from the *Periodicals* module of the PTC and on named entities of type PERSON. In the selected sample, the AMR parser identified 2262 instances of person Named Entities, 2108 of which were linked to a Wikipedia page. We then tried to retrieve the correspondent Wikidata ID (QID) of the Wikipedia pages linked by BLINK, to access the corresponding entity's date of birth (DoB) through the Wikidata property P569 (*date of birth*). We could retrieve the QID of 2006 out of the 2108 Wikipedia pages linked.

Figure 2.3: AMR graph resulting from the text2AMR parsing powered by [26, SPRING] of the sentence "J.T. Imbault was born at Paris in 1753.", extrapolated from *The Quarterly Musical Magazine And Review*, n. 25 (1825), part of the *Periodicals* module of the PTC¹⁵.

In the 102 cases where we could not retrieve a QID, the reason for the missed retrieval was that the entity linking was incorrect. This happened in cases in which the Wikipedia link pointed to a nonexistent Wikipedia page due to hallucinations in the generation of the graph. This hallucination occurs more often when the person Named Entities superficial mention in the text presents OCR errors, as shown in Figure 2.3. In the sentence, J.T. IMBAULT is the OCR-compromised superficial mention of J. J. Imbault, corresponding to Wikidata's QID Q20538968. As we can see in Figure 2.4, BLINK links J.T. IMBAULT to a nonexistent Wikipedia page, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/J._T._Imbault.

Out of the 2006 retrieved QID, we could retrieve 1402 dates of birth: by comparing the retrieved DoB to the publication date of the periodicals in which the related mention of the person Named Entities occurred, we could verify that 1199

J. T. Imbault

Article [Talk](#)

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Wikipedia does not have an article with this exact name. Please [search for J. T. Imbault in Wikipedia](#) to check for alternative titles or spellings.

- You need to [log in or create an account](#) to create this page.
- [Search for "J. T. Imbault"](#) in existing articles.
- [Look for pages within Wikipedia that link to this title.](#)

Figure 2.4: Screenshot of the Wikipedia page (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/J._T._Imbault) corresponding to the entity linked by [14, BLINK] in the sentence reported in Figure 2.3.

out of 1402 QIDs belonged to *plausible*¹⁸ named entities (namely, whose date of birth preceded that of the periodical issue) while 203 QIDs belonged to *not plausible* named entities (namely, whose date of birth followed that of the periodical issue). In the 604 cases in which we failed to retrieve a date of birth, the reason for the missed retrieval was that the entity linking was not correct (the Wikipedia page was not that of a person named entity, but that of a family name, a disambiguation page, etc.).

Checking the automatically retrieved person Named Entities entities against Wikidata’s knowledge base allowed us to assess that *at least*¹⁹ 909 out of the 2108 instances of person named entities’ Wikipedia pages linked by BLINK (43%) were wrong. Namely, they were: 1. Wikipedia pages for which we could not retrieve a related QID; 2. Wikipedia pages whose QID was that of a person named entity whose date of birth (DoB) followed the date of issue of the periodical.

On contemporary text, BLINK scores an overall accuracy of a minimum of 0.6825 on CLUEWEB - WNED-CWEB (CWEB) [39] to a maximum of 0.9087 on TAC-KBP 2010²⁰, while according to the results of our exploratory studies its performance is much lower, indicating plenty of room for improvement on NERC and EL off-the-shelf models employed in the PKE¹⁶ framework. Such an improvement can be achieved, among the other approaches, by fine-tuning the off-the-shelf models on historical data or by implementing custom filters to refine the off-the-shelf models’ output by leveraging knowledge, such as temporal and named entity’s type information stored in KBs such as Wikidata.

2.4. MHERCL, a new benchmark for HEL

In this section, we describe MHERCL, the new benchmark that we introduce as a test set for NERC and EL on historical documents. We describe how we selected the sentences that are part of the sample, the annotation guidelines, and the Inter-annotator Agreement (IAA) obtained. Also, we present the statistics of the benchmark and describe its release’s format.

2.4.1. Dataset Composition

2.4.1.1. Sampling

MHERCL v1.0 is made of manually annotated sentences extrapolated from the PTC’s historical documents. It is larger than other existing test sets in English language (cfr. sub-section 2.2.1) and, because of PTC focus on music,

¹⁸In this Chapter, we use the term *plausible* to refer to person named entities whose date of birth, according to Wikidata, preceded that of the music periodical’s issue date. We use the term *not plausible* to refer to person named entities whose date of birth, according to Wikidata, followed that of the music periodical’s issue date.

¹⁹The person Named Entities entities’ Wikipedia pages linked by BLINK whose respective named entities’ QID had a plausible DoB can be either correct or wrong, so the total number of wrong entities can be higher.

²⁰<https://catalog.ldc.upenn.edu/LDC2018T16>

it provides a unique domain-specific gaze on the EL problem. This first release of the benchmark addressed a sample of the English *Periodicals*²¹ module of the corpus, whose documents' publication dates range from 1823 to 1900. We have selected the sentences for the manual annotation based on four criteria: (1) Language (*English*); (2) Source (the *Periodicals* module of the PTC¹⁵) - we chose historical periodicals because of their similarity to historical newspapers, a textual genre at the centre of historical NERC and EL annotation campaigns (cfr. 2.2.1); (3) Being part of the *Filtered AMR Graphs Bank*¹⁷ (filtered output of the PKE¹⁶ framework); (4) Containing at least one named entity recognised by the PKE¹⁶ framework²².

We initiated our benchmark development with the *English* language due to its greater scope for comparison with other contemporary-text benchmarks, particularly in the context of model evaluation. We opted to extrapolate the sentences of MHERCL v1.0 from the *Periodicals* module of the PTC¹⁵ to align closely with the prevailing document types already utilised in existing benchmarks within the field. Historical newspaper is the dominant document type used in HIPE-2022 data [31]. We picked sentences that were part of our *Filtered AMR Graphs Bank*¹⁷ to be able to contextually check the off-the-shelf NERC and EL predictions part of the AMR graphs output of the PKE¹⁶ framework. In addition, we manually selected 196 sentences from the same corpus module. The criteria for the manual selection were sentence length (the annotators were instructed to select sentences whose length was between 30 and 70 tokens) and rich in terms of named entities' presence.

2.4.1.2. Annotation Guidelines

The sentences included in the sample described in Section 2.4.1.1 underwent manual annotations thanks to the work of two annotators (selected from Foreign Languages and Literature undergraduate students at the University of Bologna) that have received *ad hoc* training on the NERC and EL annotation task.

Generally, the annotation work was performed under the criteria that a named entity is a real-world thing indicating a unique individual through a proper noun [17]. The annotation work of the interns involved inspecting the sentences and identifying the named entities, eventually linking them to their corresponding Wikidata ID (QID).

Named entities were recognised, classified and linked following the AMR named entity annotations guidelines²³. The types were assigned according to the AMR annotation guidance instructions²⁴ and extrapolated from the AMR named entity types list²⁵.

A full description of the types used for NEs classification in MHERCL v1.0 is provided in Appendix A. Annotation guidelines are extensively described in Appendix B of this report.

2.4.1.3. IAA

Table 2.2: MHERCL v1.0 - Entity Linking IAA

#sents	#tokens (Tot.)	#tokens (Annotated)		Krippendorff's alpha
		#matching	#unmatching	
101	6.589	656	124	0,82

Inter-annotator agreement (IAA) measures the reliability of human annotations by estimating consistency among annotators. To measure IAA, we made two annotators independently annotate 101 sentences. We calculated *Krippendorff's alpha* [40] for nominal metric on the resulting annotations using Fast Krippendorff [41]. We opted for

²¹Full metadata of the *Periodicals* module of the Polifonia Textual Corpus are available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6671912>

²²In this report, it is assumed that this criterion has been used for sampling purposes. The sentences contained in MHERCL v1.0, in certain cases, do not contain any named entities.

²³<https://amr.isi.edu/doc/amr-dict.html#named%20entity>

²⁴<https://www.isi.edu/~ulf/amr/lib/popup/ne-type-selection.html>

²⁵<https://www.isi.edu/~ulf/amr/lib/ne-types.html>

Krippendorff's α for its flexibility and resilience in handling missing values, as demonstrated by its successful usage in other contexts [42]. As reported in Table 2.2, we obtained the following result: 0.82654.

2.4.1.3.1. Error examples The cases of not matching annotations between the two annotators reported in Table 2.2 can be attributed to the elevated complexity inherent to historical entity linking. The named entity mention occurring in the sentence is a historical name for that entity, used in the times in which the periodical from which the sentence is extrapolated was issued but not in use anymore in current times. Analysing two examples is interesting to understand the complexity of the EL task on historical documents. One case relates to the named entity mention `Court Magazine`, occurring in the sentence with text *I find the following sensible critical remarks among my papers; they were copied from a weekly work (the Court Magazine, I think)* and with ID `TheHarmonicon__1833-005.txt_1585`. One user assigned the label `NIL` to this named entity mention, which indicates the fact that the named entity is not included in Wikidata. The other assigned the QID `Q3206551`²⁶, which relates to the Wikipedia page for *La Belle Assemblée*²⁷, in which we can read the following passage, which justifies the choice of assigning the QID `Q3206551`:

The magazine was published as La Belle Assemblée from 1806 until May 1832. It became The Court Magazine and Belle Assemblée from 1832 to 1837. After 1837 the Belle Assemblée name was dropped when the magazine merged with the Lady's Magazine and Museum (itself a merger of The Lady's Magazine and a competitor) to become The Court Magazine and Monthly Critic.

The other is the case for the named entity mention `Court of Vienna`, occurring in the sentence with text *Sommer, organist to the Court of Vienna; this is the greatest compliment which can be paid to his talents.* and with ID `TheQuarterlyMusicalMagazineAndReview__1828-037.txt_1570`. One user assigned the label `NIL` to this named entity mention, while the other assigned the QID `Q209937`²⁸, which relates to the Wikipedia page for the *Vienna State Opera*²⁹, in which we can read the following passage:

The Vienna State Opera [...] is an opera house and opera company based in Vienna, Austria. [...] It was built from 1861 to 1869 following plans by August Sicard von Sicardsburg and Eduard van der Nüll, and designs by Josef Hlávka. The opera house was inaugurated as the "Vienna Court Opera" (Wiener Hofoper) in the presence of Emperor Franz Joseph I and Empress Elisabeth of Austria. It became known by its current name after establishing the First Austrian Republic in 1921.

The above passage misled the annotator who assigned the QID `Q209937`: in fact, the opera house was renowned with the name "Vienna Court Opera" after its building, which dates back to 1861-1869, which in any case is after the issue of the periodical that mentions it.

Before releasing MHERCL, we solved the disagreement cases by aligning them to the Annotation Guidelines to make sure that the released benchmark did not present wrong annotations due to disagreement.

2.4.1.4. Statistics

Table 2.3: MHERCL v1.0 - Dataset Stats

Dataset	Lang.	#docs	#sents	#tokens
MHERCL v1.0	EN	76	875	27.549

As summarised in Table 2.3, MHERCL v1.0 is made of 875 sentences, extrapolated from 76 documents (historical periodicals). As reported in Table 2.4, MHERCL v1.0 includes 1.829 unique named entities belonging to 59 different

²⁶<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q3206551>

²⁷https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/La_Belle_Assembl%C3%A9e

²⁸<https://www.wikidata.org/wiki/Q209937>

²⁹https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Vienna_State_Opera

Table 2.4: MHERCL v1.0 - Named Entities Superficial Mentions Stats

	#mention	#types	noisy	NIL
all	2.378	N/A	0, 14	0, 30
unique	1.829	59	N/A	0, 38

Table 2.5: Top 10 named entity types occurring in MHERCL v1.0

named entity type	#occurrences
PERSON	1.253
CITY	251
MUSIC	188
ORGANIZATION	94
WORK-OF-ART	85
COUNTRY	78
BUILDING	52
OPERA	52
THEATRE	41
WORSHIP-PLACE	41

types. On the total of annotated named entity mentions, 30% could not be linked to a QID. Those are cases in which the annotators could not identify a Wikidata entry corresponding to the named entity's mention. Those cases are annotated with the label `NIL`. On the total of annotated named entity mentions, 0, 14 are *noisy*, namely impacted by errors due to OCR. Quantifying the noisy entities is important to facilitate downstream qualitative error analysis of NERC and EL systems and for comparison with other historical datasets [31].

Table 2.5 reports, in order of frequency, the top 10 NEs types occurring in MHERCL v1.0. The types distribution reveals MHERCL v1.0 specificity to the music domain due to the presence of domain-specific types such as `MUSIC`, `OPERA`, `WORK-OF-ART`. A full description of the types used for NEs classification in MHERCL v1.0 is provided in Appendix A.

2.4.1.5. Format

MHERCL v1.0 is released in CoNLL-U format ³⁰ through its dedicated GitHub repository³¹. An example of an annotated sentence is reported below:

```
#document_id:DwightSJournalOfMusic__1873-016.txt_762
#document_date:1873
#sent_text:A native of Parma, ateighteen years of age Jong was received into
the Conservatory of Music of that town, where Jong soon made himself.a
name as the most promising pupil of the institution.
A      O      _      a      DET
native O      _      native NOUN
of     O      _      of     ADP
Parma  B-city  Q2683  Parma  PROP
,      O      _      ,      PUNCT
ateighteen  O      _      ateighteen  NUM
```

³⁰<https://universaldependencies.org/format.html>

³¹https://github.com/polifonia-project/historical-entity-linking/blob/main/benchmark/v0.1/mhercl_v01.tsv

years	0	—	year	NOUN		
of	0	—	of	ADP		
age	0	—	age	NOUN		
	0	—	'	PUNCT		
Jong	B-person		NIL	Jong	PROPN	
was	0	—	be	AUX		
received		0	—	receive	VERB	
into	0	—	into	ADP		
the	0	—	the	DET		
Conservatory	B-school		Q1439627	Conservatory	PROPN	
of	I-school		Q1439627	of	ADP	
Music	I-school		Q1439627	Music	PROPN	
of	0	—	of	ADP		
that	0	—	that	DET		
town	0	—	town	NOUN		
,	0	—	,	PUNCT		
where	0	—	where	SCONJ		
	0	—	'	PUNCT		
Jong	B-person		NIL	Jong	PROPN	
soon	0	—	soon	ADV		
made	0	—	make	VERB		
himself.a		0	—	himself.a	PRON	
name	0	—	name	NOUN		
as	0	—	as	ADP		
the	0	—	the	DET		
most	0	—	most	ADV		
promising		0	—	promising	ADJ	
pupil	0	—	pupil	NOUN		
of	0	—	of	ADP		
the	0	—	the	DET		
institution		0	—	institution	NOUN	
.	0	—	.	PUNCT		

In the above example, we can see that rows beginning with # contain metadata. In more details:

- #DOCUMENT_ID, provides the PTC¹⁵'s ID of the document the sentence is extrapolated from;
- #DOCUMENT_DATE, provides the date in which the document was published;
- #SENT_TEXT, provides the text of the annotated sentence.

. The columns can be explained as follows:

- COLUMN 0 reports the sentence's tokens, one per row;
- COLUMN 1, reports BIO³² tags and type label of the named entity;
- COLUMN 2, reports the Wikidata QID assigned by the annotators to the identified named entity;
- COLUMN 3, reports the token's base form (lemma);
- COLUMN 4, reports the token's Part of Speech (PoS) tag.

MHERCL v1.0 format has been designed to comply with HIPE-2022 data (which is based on IOB and CoNLL-U), facilitating future integration.

³²According to BIO notation tagging format, each token which constitutes the beginning of a named entity string is assigned the label 'B' (an abbreviation of 'beginning'). Each token which falls within a named entity string is assigned the label 'I' (an abbreviation for 'inside'). Each token standing outside of a named entity string is assigned the label 'O' (an abbreviation for 'outside').

2.5. Models

Given the issues of existing entity linkers in HEL, as shown in Section 2.1, it becomes apparent that a new generation of models that are able to capture the peculiarities of historical documents needs to be investigated. This involves natively taking into account the historical nature of the documents, i.e. entities that did not exist at the time of writing of the document should not be considered. Moreover, since such entities lie on the long tail of most KBs, a way to reduce the popularity bias that guides those models to the prediction of wrong links must be investigated. To this end, we propose two different methods that rely on different assumptions to support entity linkers in HEL tasks. HEL, described in Section 2.5.1, is a method that produces consistent labelling of the data using game-theoretic principles. Informally, the model considers each token in a sentence as an agent that plays games with other neighbouring tokens and obtains rewards at each iteration. The games are implemented as a selection of possible entities, and the rewards are constructed as a payoff function that the players try to maximize by selecting strategies that are consistent with the ones selected by the co-players. In this way, computing the equilibrium state of the game dynamics allows the model to reach a situation in which each player is playing its best strategy, i.e., the strategy that gives the highest payoff. C-BLINK, described in Section 2.5.2, pursues a different path. Rather than proposing a new method, we modify BLINK such that it takes into account the *plausibility* of an entity during the candidate generation phase. A *plausible* candidate, in the context of HEL, is a candidate whose type loosely matches the automatically extracted NER and whose associated date is antecedent to the document from which the sentence is extracted. Type and date information are obtained through the use of an external KB (Wikidata). The distillation of those constraints into BLINK does not require any training, but rather reduces the pool of candidates that are considered by it during the inference phase. Moreover, by assuming that only *plausible* entities are considered, we devise a mechanism that makes C-BLINK able to output *NIL* linkage - i.e. it is possible to know when it is not possible to link an entity since each candidate considered is not fit enough.

2.5.1. ELD

Our approach to EL assumes that the disambiguation process underlying this task has to be coherent with the context in which entities appear, respecting time and logical constraints. To this end, we developed ELD (Entity Linking Dynamics), an innovative model that is grounded on relaxation labelling processes [43]. This class of algorithms can produce consistent labelling of the data thanks to the use of constraints among labels (entities in the context of EL) designed to make the label assigned to an object consistent with the labels assigned to the other objects in the same batch (sentence or paragraph in the context of EL). Relaxation labeling processes have been used successfully in different fields, including computer vision [27], NLP [44], and graph processing [45]. Relaxation labelling has also been formulated in terms of game theory [46] by interpreting the objects to be labelled as the players of a non-cooperative game [47] and the constraints on labels as the strategies that the players can select to play the game. We recall here that in game theory, the players are considered rational and select the strategy that maximises a predefined payoff. The selection is performed considering the strategies a co-player can select in response to a strategy.

Table 2.6: An example of a payoff matrix for the game of *matching pennies*. The number on the left of each cell of the matrix indicates the payoff obtained by player 1, and the number on the right indicates the payoff of player 2. Player 1 plays according to the rows of the matrix, and player 2 with the columns.

		PLAYER 2	
		heads	tails
PLAYER 1	heads	1 -1	-1 1
	tails	-1 1	1 -1

This information is stored in a payoff matrix (see Table 2.6) that defines the game. In this example, it is defined as the game of matching pennies, in which player 1 wins if both players select the same face of the penny and player 2 wins if both players do not select the same face. The top left cell of the payoff matrix depicts the situation in which

player 1 selects heads and player 2 selects heads. The outcome of this game is a payoff of 1 for player 1 and a payoff of -1 for player 2. As it can be seen, the outcome of a game does not depend on the strategy selected by a single player but on the combination of the strategies selected by the players involved in the game. An equilibrium state for the game of *matching pennies* is to use a mixed strategy in which heads and tails are played with the same probability. In this way, it would be difficult for a co-player to guess the strategy that will be used.

More formally, game dynamics consists of a finite set of players $N = (1, \dots, n)$, a finite set of pure strategies $S_i = \{1, \dots, m_i\}$ for each player $i \in N$, and a payoff (utility) function $u_i : S \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$, that associates a payoff with each combination of strategies in $S = S_1 \times S_2 \times \dots \times S_n$. A player i , in addition to playing single (pure) strategies from S_i , can also use mixed strategies, that are probability distributions over pure strategies. A mixed strategy over S_i is defined as a vector $\mathbf{x}_i = (x_1, \dots, x_{m_i})$, such that $x_j \geq 0$ and $\sum x_j = 1$. Each mixed strategy corresponds to a point in the simplex Δ_{m_i} , whose corners correspond to pure strategies. The intuition is that player i randomises over strategies according to the probabilities in x_i . Each mixed strategy profile lives in the mixed strategy space of the game, given by the Cartesian product $\Theta = \Delta_{m_1} \times \Delta_{m_2} \times \dots \times \Delta_{m_n}$. In a two-player game, a strategy profile can be defined as a pair (x_i, x_j) . The expected payoff for this strategy profile is computed as:

$$u(x_i, x_j) = \mathbf{x}_i^\top \cdot A_{ij} x_j, \quad (2.1)$$

where A_{ij} is the $m_i \times m_j$ payoff matrix between players i and j . The payoff corresponding to the h -th pure strategy is computed as:

$$u(\mathbf{x}_i) = \mathbf{x}_i \cdot \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} (A_{ij} x_j)^h, \quad (2.2)$$

this payoff is additively separable. The summation is over all the n_i players with whom i is playing. The average payoff of player i is calculated as:

$$u(\mathbf{x}_i) = \sum_{h=1}^{m_i} u(x_i^h). \quad (2.3)$$

To find the Nash equilibrium of the game, that corresponds to a situation in which each player is playing his best mixed strategy, it is common to use the discrete time version of the replicator dynamics equation [48] for each player $i \in N$,

$$x_i^h(t+1) = x_i^h(t) \frac{u(x_i^h)}{u(\mathbf{x}_i)} \forall h \in \mathbf{x}_i \quad (2.4)$$

This equation allows better-than-average strategies to grow at each iteration. It can be considered an inductive learning process in which the players learn from past experiences how to play their best strategy. In the context of EL, it can be seen as the process that allows to associate each mention (player) in a text with the most consistent entity (strategy) in that specific context (game).

2.5.1.1. Implementation

The EL task is modelled in ELD performing at the same time also the Word Sense Disambiguation (WSD), i.e., associating each content word in a sentence with its meaning as encoded in a KB such as WordNet [49]. This formulation of the problem allows the exploitation of contextual information to perform consistent data labelling, disambiguating entities and considering nouns and verbs around them. As we will see later, it is possible to model EL and WSD together thanks to a shared vector space for the computation of the feature vectors of both tasks.

The pipeline of our model is presented in Figure 2.5. ELD takes as input a text that is pre-processed with a tokeniser, a part-of-speech tagger and a named entity recognition tagger to obtain a set of annotations $T = ((t_1, pos_1, ner_1), (t_2, pos_2, ner_2), \dots, (t_n, pos_n, ner_n))$ (step 1). In addition to this annotation, the text is also fed into a PLM to obtain a contextualised representation of each token $E = (e_1, e_2, \dots, e_n)$, since the tokenisations in T and E are different (E uses subtokens), we average the subtoken representations in E to match the tokenisation in T (step 2). This step allows to obtain a feature vector for each token in T , which results in a $n \times w$ matrix W in

Figure 2.5: The pipeline of ELD. Vectors with red borders represent the strategy space distribution of an entity. It is updated at each iteration of the system, calculating the payoff that each strategy (entity id) obtains playing with all its neighbours, both entities (player j in this example) and non-entity words (player k and z in this example) represented with blue border vectors. Once the payoffs are computed, the vector of player i is normalised to obtain a new distribution used at the system’s next iteration. This update is performed for all the players at each iteration of the system until it converges.

which only the n nouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs and named entities in T are maintained (w refers to the number of dimensions of the feature vectors). These n tokens are the players of the game dynamics implemented in ELD. With the embedding matrix W , it is possible to create the $n \times n$ matrix A that encodes pairwise similarity information among each embedding in W . This information will be used by ELD to weigh each player’s influence on another in a way in which similar players have a more considerable reciprocal influence in the strategy selection. For example, in the following sentence:

1. Abe Lincoln played the guitar in the Dinosaurs band for 20 years.

the word *guitar* can influence more than the word *years* the linking of the mention *Abe Lincoln* toward the entity *Abe_Lincoln_(guitarist)* than towards the entity *Abe_Lincoln_(politician)*. This information can be obtained constructing a payoff matrix that encodes the similarity between the word *guitar* and the entities *Abe_Lincoln_(guitarist)* and *Abe_Lincoln_(politician)*.

Once the tokenisations are obtained, the candidate generation is performed in step 3, i.e., selecting the possible senses/entities to which a word/mention can refer. For this operation, we used two different knowledge bases: WordNet for the selection of the senses of nouns, verbs, adjectives and adverbs, and Wikidata for the selection of entities connected to a mention marked as named entity. With this information it is possible to define the m_i strategies that each player i can select as $S_i = (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_{m_i})$. The single strategy spaces allow to create the strategy space of the game as the set of different strategies of each player $S = s_1, s_2, \dots, s_m$. This information is then used to create other two matrices used by ELD. The first one is the $n \times m$ matrix X that represents the strategy space of the game as a probability distribution. Each player uses the resulting probability vector as a mixed strategy with m elements (strategies not in the strategy space of a player have 0 probability). The strategy space can be initialised using a uniform distribution with the following equation:

$$x_i^h = \begin{cases} |m_i|^{-1} & \text{if sense/entity } h \text{ is in } S_i, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases} \quad (2.5)$$

or with a prior if it is available, substituting $|m_i|^{-1}$ in Equation 2.5 with the frequency of the corresponding sense/entity and normalising \mathbf{x}_i to make it sum up to 1.

The second one is the $m \times d$ matrix D in which each sense/entity is represented as an embedding. To make sense of entity embedding, we used embeddings created with the same methodology to have them both in the same vector space. Sense embedding is obtained using Ares embeddings [50] that employs a multilingual language model to embed text annotated with WSD information and to combine the resulting representations for each distinct sense. We followed the same procedure to develop the entity embeddings, embedding text annotated with EL information with the same multilingual language model used by Ares, i.e., mBERT [51]. This step allows also to have a model that can work on multiple languages without any modification. With the embedding matrix D , it is possible to create the $m \times m$ matrix Z that encodes pairwise similarity information among each embedding in D . This matrix represents the payoff matrix of the games so that the payoff is higher if two senses/entities are similar. This operation will allow to maintain the textual coherence and to force players to select strategies that are related, such as the sense of *guitar* as a musical instrument and an musician entity or two entities that are contemporary or connected such as a composer and his instructor.

Once these sources of information are computed, ELD can be started by using the replicator dynamic equation [52] in Equation 2.5.1, where the payoff of strategy h for player i is calculated as:

$$u(x_i^h) = x_i^h \cdot \sum_{j=1}^{n_i} (A_{ij} Z \mathbf{x}_j)^h \quad (2.6)$$

where n_i are the neighbours of player i as in the graph A . The average payoff is calculated as:

$$u(\mathbf{x}_i) = \sum_{h=1}^{m_i} u(x_i^h) \quad (2.7)$$

Table 2.7: Datasets Stats

	set	Lang.	#docs	#tokens	# entities	noisy	NLL
	MHERCL	v1.0	EN	76	27.549	2.378	0,14 0,30
	HIPE2020	test	EN	46	16.635	449	0,05 0,40

2.5.2. C-BLINK

Following the approach in 2.5.1, i.e. the disambiguation process underlying the EL task has to be coherent with respect to constraints, we developed C-BLINK (Constrained BLINK) as an extension of BLINK [14]. Our model improves the model proposed in BLINK by constraining the model to only consider *plausible* entities during the linking process. A *plausible* entity is, in general, an entity that satisfies a set of given constraints.

In the context of HEL, one of the plausibility conditions is that the entity must satisfy some temporal condition. For example, in the sentence of Figure 2.1

(4) Fabio Constantini flourished about the year 1630, and ultimately became maestro at the chapel of Loretto.

the mention *Fabio Constantini* is aligned to the entity *Claudio Constantini*. The alignment is implausible since the sentence is extracted from a periodical dated 1824 while *Claudio Constantini* was born in 1983. The alignment is hence unreasonable from a logical standpoint.

The plausibility of an entity is not limited to HEL. As also argued by Tedeschi et al. [53], confusion in the linking process can be prevented by filtering the set of entities that the model considers as possible entities to align. This has been done by relying on the classification of an extended NER model that classifies entities in a set of fine-grained classes. All the possible entities are filtered based on the NER class of the mention. The remaining entities

are all *plausible*, and the model only needs to learn which one is more suited to be aligned rather than figuring out if an entity is also *plausible*. The results are shown to largely outperform the compared models in several benchmarks. C-BLINK follows the arguments of Tedeschi et al. [53] by proposing a method to systematically filter out *implausible* entities without retraining the model from scratch. As addressed in Section 2.2.2, BLINK is an EL model that retrieves a set of candidates by matching the entity mention to the candidates' description. The candidate descriptions are extracted from Wikipedia and encoded by a BERT-based model, called *bi-encoder*. The *bi-encoder* is fine-tuned to maximise the cosine similarity between the vector encoding of the sentence and the mention. Since the similarity computed by the *bi-encoder* might be largely due to the similarity between the superficial mention, another component is used to re-rank the results, called the *cross-encoder*.

Hence, we can see the EL process of BLINK as a two-step process:

- The *bi-encoder* is trained to hypothesise a set of entities that can be linked with the mention;
- The *cross-encoder* is trained to further process the entities such that the target mention emerges from the other proposed entities.

We integrate the plausibility check in the *bi-encoder* component B . In particular, let Φ be a collection of boolean functions that checks whether an entity e is plausible given a mention m . For example, we can see the approach of Tedeschi et al. [53] as the function $\phi_t \in \Phi$ where $\phi_t(m, e) = 1$ if and only if the class predicted for m by the NER model is the same as the class predicted for e . In the context of HEL, we can define $\phi_d \in \Phi$ as the function such that $\phi_d(m, e) = 1$ if and only if the date associated to m is compatible with the one of e . In the example above, $\phi(\text{Fabio Constantini, Claudio Constantini}) = 0$.

The integration in BLINK is done by directly annihilating the similarity scores of implausible entities. This is done by extending the scoring function s implemented by the *bi-encoder* to:

$$s(m, e) = s(m, e) \cdot \sum_{\phi \in \Phi} \phi(m, e) \quad (2.8)$$

Note that $s(m, e) = 0$ for every e that is implausible with respect to m . Each function $\phi \in \Phi$ can be a *rule-based* function or any arbitrary function, including a neural network. In the latter case, m and s are replaced by the vector representations \mathbf{x}_m and \mathbf{x}_e computed by the *bi-encoder*.

2.5.2.1. Taking NIL into account

While the plausibility constraint prevents the model from hypothesising logically inconsistent entities, this does not guarantee the soundness of the final prediction. Indeed, if the target entity that corresponds to the mention is not part of the pool of entities considered in the model, it is impossible to provide a correct prediction. In this case, it is desirable to have a model that can predict a `NIL` link - i.e. the result is that the link is not possible since it is not in the pool of all the possible candidates. This is a fundamental property in many scenarios and particularly in HEL, where it might happen that the mentioned entities are not available in any Knowledge Base. Given the updated scoring function of Equation 2.8, we can safely assume that the candidates produced by the *bi-encoder* are all plausible entities with respect to the set of functions Φ . Additionally, we can assume that the candidates with the higher probability of being the correct entity scored higher than the others since the model has been trained specifically for this task. It follows that there must exist an entity whose score is higher than all the other entities. Many approaches have been proposed to detect whether the highest score is significant enough or `NIL` should be predicted, such as training a binary classifier or defining a threshold on the score [54]. With \mathbf{s}_c the vector containing the top-k scores for each candidate, produced by either the *bi-encoder* or the *cross-encoder*, we propose two different heuristics to predict `NIL`. In the first heuristic, we predict `NIL` if the highest score is not significantly higher than the mean of the top-k candidates' scores. Considering the variance of the top-k candidates' scores, if the target entity is not within the candidates we expect a low variance in the scores since all the entities are similarly fit as a prediction (according to the *bi-encoder*) and they are all plausible. If on the other hand, the target entity is within the candidates, then one

of the scores must be much higher than the others. Hence, we predict `NIL` whenever the condition

$$\frac{2|\mu(\mathbf{s}_c) - (\mathbf{s}_c)_1|}{\mu(\mathbf{s}_c) + (\mathbf{s}_c)_1} \leq \tau \quad (2.9)$$

holds, where $\mu(\mathbf{s}_c)$ is the arithmetic mean of \mathbf{s}_c and τ is the threshold. Equation 2.9 computes the percentage deviation between the highest score and the arithmetic mean of all the scores. Intuitively, if Equation 2.9 holds then the first score is not distinguishable from the others and the model is not confident enough in the prediction. Hence, `NIL` should be predicted.

In the second heuristic, we propose to leverage the Levenshtein distance lev between e and m . If $lev(m, e) \leq \tau$ holds we predict `NIL`. This is done since after the application of the plausibility filter, if the best candidate retrieved is not similar at all to m , it should be discarded regardless of its score.

2.6. Experimental setup

2.6.1. Datasets

The evaluation of ELD is performed on two datasets: HIPE-2022 and our newly released benchmark MHERCL v1.0. On the overall multilingual HIPE-2022 data³³, for the scope of this deliverable, we concentrate only on the data in English language, because MHERCL v1.0 includes only English language text. AJMC DATASET¹² and *Classical Commentaries* textual genres diverge significantly from the ones contained in MHERCL v1.0. Also, the tagset used in TOPRES19th¹³ is very narrow, focusing exclusively on toponyms. Consequently, we opted to include in our experiments only the English data released within HIPE2020¹⁴.

The statistics of MHERCL v1.0 and English data of HIPE2020¹⁴ are presented in Table 2.7.

2.6.2. Models

Our evaluation was conducted by comparing the results of three models: ELD, BLINK and the model proposed by [34, L3i]. The model proposed by [34, L3i], as described in Section 2.2.2, is the model that ranked higher in CLEF-HIPE-2022 for the EL task on HIPE2020 English data. ELD and BLINK can be considered as general models. For this reason, we implemented five versions for them, with different candidate selection functionalities that we describe in the paragraphs below.

Time The first criterion upon which we based our candidate retention functionalities is the comparison between (a) MHERCL v1.0, or HIPE-2020, documents' date of publication, which are given as metadata in the datasets; (b) the information extracted by retrieving the value of the time-related Wikidata properties labels per candidate. If (b) chronologically follows (a), the candidate is filtered out from the list by the model that has this functionality activated. We report the time-related Wikidata properties that we considered in our experiments in Table 2.8. The properties' retrieval order has been set according to a qualitative analysis of the semantics of the properties' names and descriptions. The analysis aimed to ensure to retain, when available, the most precise properties' values, such as P569 - DATE OF BIRTH (ranked first), against less precise ones, such as P585 - POINT IN TIME (ranked last).

Type The second criterion upon which we based our candidate retention functionalities is the comparison between (a) the gold NER class (*type*) assigned to the superficial named entity mentioned by the human annotators (for details about the types used in MHERCL v1.0, see Appendix A; for details about the types used in HIPE-2020, see [30, 31]); (b) the *types* extracted by retrieving the value of P31 - 'INSTANCE OF' Wikidata property's labels per candidate. Mapping rules between (a) and (b) were established. (a) was extended by adding its more generic

³³<https://github.com/hipe-eval/HIPE-2022-data/tree/main>

Table 2.8: Time-related Wikidata properties used for candidate retention functionalities

Retrieval Order	Wikidata property	Name	Description
1	P569	DATE OF BIRTH	date on which the subject was born
2	P571	INCEPTION	time when an entity begins to exist
3	P1619	DATE OF OFFICIAL OPENING	date or point in time an event, museum, theater etc. officially opened
4	P1191	DATE OF FIRST PERFORMANCE	date a work was first debuted, performed or live-broadcasted
5	P10135	RECORDING DATE	the date when a recording was made
6	P577	PUBLICATION DATE	date or point in time when a work was first published or released
7	P575	TIME OF DISCOVERY OR INVENTION	date or point in time when the item was discovered or invented
8	P1317	FLORUIT	date when the person was known to be active or alive, when birth or death not documented
9	P7124	DATE OF THE FIRST ONE	qualifier: when the first element of a quantity appeared/took place
10	P10673	DEBUT DATE	date when a person or group is considered to have "debuted"
11	P9448	INTRODUCED ON	date when a bill was introduced into a legislature
12	P6949	ANNOUNCEMENT DATE	time of the first public presentation of a subject by the creator, of information by the media
13	P729	SERVICE ENTRY	date or point in time on which a piece or class of equipment entered operational service
14	P2031	WORK PERIOD (START)	start of period during which a person or group flourished (fl. = "floruit") in their professional activity
15	P585	POINT IN TIME	time and date something took place, existed or a statement was true

type(s) according to an *ad-hoc* taxonomy (see Appendix A) designed for the dataset. If (a) is not included in (b), the candidate is filtered out from the list by the model that has this functionality activated.

NIL As reported in 2.5.2, we want C-BLINK to predict **NIL** when the link is not possible within the pool of candidates. We experiment with two heuristics to accomplish such a goal. In the first heuristic, we predict **NIL** if the percentage deviation between the highest score and the arithmetic mean of all the candidates' scores is lower than a certain threshold ($perc_dev_T$). In the second heuristic, we predict **NIL**, if the Levenshtein distance between the gold and the candidate mentions, is lower than a certain threshold (lev_T). This is done since after the application of the plausibility filter, if the best candidate retrieved is not similar at all to m , it should be discarded regardless of its score. To determine the thresholds for the two heuristics, we use HIPE-2022 as a development set and test thresholds from 0,5 to 0,001. The detailed results are depicted in Figures 2.6, 2.7, 2.8, 2.8, 2.9. We finally select the one that ensures the higher F1 score: for C-BLINK_{dot time-type}, it is 0.025 for $perc_dev_T$ and 0,448 for lev_T ; while in C-BLINK_{all time-type}, it is 0.123 for lev_T and any values from 0,5 to 0,001 for $perc_dev_T$, because the cross-encoder architecture in [14, BLINK], when re-scoring the candidates, normalises their scores so that it is not possible to identify a candidate whose percentage deviation over the arithmetic mean of all candidate's score is significant. We apply the thresholds providing best results on HIPE-2020 dataset also to C-BLINK runs on MHERCL v1.0.

2.6.2.1. Settings

The functionalities were activated or deactivated to assess which component contributes more to the performance of the model:

1. Model: <MODEL> - Functionality: "DOT". In this case, BLINK is used by activating only its *bi-encoder* component, which is a BERT-based model fine-tuned to maximise the cosine similarity between the vector encoding of the sentence and the mention. ELD simply computes the similarity among the embedding of a mention with the embeddings of its candidates. The candidate with the highest similarity is selected as the entity to link to the mention;
2. Model: <MODEL> - Functionality: "ALL". In this case, BLINK is used by activating also its *cross-encoder* component, which is used to re-rank the results. For ELD, the payoff is computed as described in Section 2.5.1.1 and all candidates retrieved from a Wikidata are retained. Also for BLINK the candidates are not filtered;
3. Model: <MODEL> - Filter: "Time". In this case, only the candidates with a date (cfr. Table 2.8) posterior to the

Figure 2.6: P, R and F1 scores of C-BLINK_{dot} time-type over the HIPE-2020 dataset as the *perc_dev_τ* changes from 0,5 and 0,001. **Figure 2.7:** P, R and F1 scores of C-BLINK_{all} time-type over the HIPE-2020 dataset as the *perc_dev_τ* changes from 0,5 and 0,001.

Figure 2.8: P, R and F1 scores of C-BLINK_{dot} time-type over the HIPE-2020 dataset as the *lev_τ* changes from 0,5 and 0,001. **Figure 2.9:** P, R and F1 scores of C-BLINK_{all} time-type over the HIPE-2020 dataset as the *lev_τ* changes from 0,5 and 0,001.

publication year of the document under analysis are retained³⁴.

4. Model: <MODEL> - Filter: "Type". In this case, only the candidates that share the same NER class with the one annotated in the benchmarks are retained.
5. Model: <MODEL> - Filter: "Time and Type". In this case, both dates and types are considered to filter the candidate list.

2.7. Results and Analysis

In this section, we present the evaluation of our models conducted on MHERCL v1.0 and HIPE2020. Aligning with [31], anytime the model's predicted link and the gold link differ, we count a false positive for the erroneous link by the model and a false negative for the missed gold link.

In the analysis of experimental results, the following observations can be made from the performances of various models on the MHERCL v1.0 (cfr. Table 2.9) and HIPE2020 (cfr. Table 2.10) benchmarks. The baseline methods, including BLINK "DOT" (biencoder only), BLINK "ALL" (biencoder+crossencoder), ELD "DOT" (ELD with candidate

³⁴This candidate retention policy is not applied to superficial named entity mentions whose NER class suggests that the entity is a location, namely CITY, CITY-DISTRICT, COUNTRY, ROAD, SQUARE, COUNTY, LOCAL-REGION, CONTINENT, MOUNTAIN, COUNTRY-REGION, PROVINCE for MHERCL v1.0, and LOC for HIPE-2022. This is because location entities, in Wikidata, often report time properties which are related to major institutional changes, such as the dates of their foundation and Republics, which are relatively recent and can be misleading.

Table 2.9: MHERCL. The results are provided as F1 where the highest value is in bold.

Model	Functionality	Filter	NIL heuristic	F1 measure
BLINK	DOT	N/A	N/A	0.52
C-BLINK	DOT	Time	N/A	0.53
C-BLINK	DOT	Type	N/A	0.53
C-BLINK	DOT	Time and Type	N/A	0.54
C-BLINK	DOT	Time and Type	lev	0.55
C-BLINK	DOT	Time and Type	perc_dev	0.73
BLINK	ALL	N/A	N/A	0.53
C-BLINK	ALL	Time	N/A	0.54
C-BLINK	ALL	Type	N/A	0.54
C-BLINK	ALL	Time and Type	N/A	0.54
C-BLINK	ALL	Time and Type	lev	0.56
C-BLINK	ALL	Time and Type	perc_dev	0.59*
ELD	DOT	N/A	N/A	0.49
ELD	rep_dyn	N/A	N/A	0.57

Table 2.10: HIPE2020. The results are provided as F1. The highest value in the Precision column is in bold, and the first result with a statistically significant difference from it, is marked with * ($\chi^2, p < 0.05$)

Model	Functionality	Filter	NIL heuristic	F1 measure
L3I[34]	-	-	-	0,54
BLINK	DOT	N/A	N/A	0.34
C-BLINK	DOT	Time	N/A	0.34
C-BLINK	DOT	Type	N/A	0.34
C-BLINK	DOT	Time and Type	N/A	0.33
C-BLINK	DOT	Time and Type	lev	0.53
C-BLINK	DOT	Time and Type	perc_dev	0.67
BLINK	ALL	N/A	N/A	0.33
C-BLINK	ALL	Time	N/A	0.34
C-BLINK	ALL	Type	N/A	0.33
C-BLINK	ALL	Time and Type	N/A	0.34
C-BLINK	ALL	Time and Type	lev	0.54
C-BLINK	ALL	Time and Type	perc_dev	0.57
ELD	DOT	N/A	N/A	0.52
ELD	rep_dyn	N/A	N/A	0.62*

retrieval only), underperformed compared to models utilizing filters and NIL heuristics.

Regarding models with candidate retrieval and reranking, ELD's rep_dyn approach (ELD with candidate retrieval + game-theory-based candidates reranking) demonstrated better performance than BLINK "ALL" (biencoder+crossencoder) on both benchmarks due to the importance of agreement between the entity mention and the entity candidate to be linked. This provides empirical evidence that the game-theoretical approach to the reranking

phase is better suited for this objective.

Models with plausibility filters activated showed some improvement, but the potential gains could be more substantial if BLINK's biencoder were fine-tuned considering these filters. Additionally, the complexities of mapping Wikidata types to benchmark-specific types hinder progress, as Wikidata types are granular and noisy compared to the coarse-grained and less noisy named entity types in each specific benchmark.

NIL heuristics are crucial due to the high presence of entities without corresponding knowledge base entries in these historical datasets. The application of the Levenshtein distance heuristic for NIL management led to improvements but with more significant effects on HIPE2020 than MHERCL v1.0. This difference may be attributed to MHERCL's specificity to the domain of music and the higher presence of OCR errors.

The NIL - perc_dev heuristic cannot generalize to both C-BLINK "DOT" and C-BLINK "ALL", as it is more effective for models without a candidates' re-ranking phase. Utilizing the confidence scores returned by encoder-only models helps identify cases where the link of an entity mention in a text to a candidate in a knowledge base is not confident enough. The issue with the crossencoder is due to an underlying assumption that the correct entity to link is always within the list proposed by the biencoder. When this is not the case, as can be seen from the results, the crossencoder still identifies a candidate as the prominent one, by boosting its score. This effectively prevents the NIL filter from detecting a sub-confident answer from the model. A possible solution involves incorporating the filter into the encoder phase so that the crossencoder receives information regarding a specific mention that should not be linked to any candidate.

The score of the model by L3i [34] team (the best-performing model at CLEF-HIPE 2022 competition) on this dataset is 0.54, which is below the score obtained by the highest score obtained by ELD (rep_dyn) and by C-BLINK "DOT" utilizing filters and NIL perc_dev heuristics. Also, in the experiments on HIPE2020, the time and type filters without the NIL heuristics do not significantly impact C-BLINK performance: when applied on C-BLINK "DOT", the filters decrease the performances of the model without filters. This is likely due to the noisy information we obtain from Wikidata, and suggests that this data must be further analyzed, refining the mapping with HIPE-2022 NERC classes (*types*) and correcting this aspect to exploit the filters' potential.

2.8. Conclusion

In this chapter, we presented MHERCL v1.0, a collection of annotated English sentences for historical named entity recognition, classification and linking. The dataset is available to the research community for further study. It is derived from historical periodicals published between 1823 and 1900 collected within the building of the Polifonia Textual Corpus¹⁶, a multilingual, multi-module and diachronic corpus on Musical Heritage. For future work that will outlive the project, we plan to expand the dataset by including annotated sentences extrapolated from Italian historical periodicals specialised in the music domain. To the best of our knowledge, there is no recently released resource of historical periodicals in Italian with annotations for the NERC and EL tasks, so contributing with a specialised benchmark in this language would significantly contribute to the community. Also, in collaboration with musicologists, we will validate the NEs that the annotators could not link to Wikidata and consider adding them as new entries to that KB.

We presented and evaluated also ELD, a new model for HEL, and C-BLINK, an extended version of the widely utilised entity linker BLINK, used in the Text-to-KG pipeline developed by WP4 for Polifonia. We developed simple methods to improve the quality of EL results based on temporal and typological filters, and proposed two heuristics for the management of NIL predictions. The model evaluation allowed us to identify some weaknesses and propose solutions for improvements. Specifically, since temporal and typological filters have been demonstrated to be beneficial, we aim to improve the quality of the data we used for this operation to possibly use it on a larger domain.

2.9. Software and Data Release

We collect in this subsection the main software and data resources of MHERCL v1.0 and ELD mentioned in Section 2 of this deliverable. Details about their compliance with the FAIR protocol is reported in Chapter 4 of this report.

- MHERCL v1.0 and ELD - Available at <https://github.com/polifonia-project/historical-entity-linking>.

3. Evaluation of knowledge extraction methods through QA

3.1. Introduction

The introduction of the transformer architecture [55] revolutionised Natural Language Processing (NLP). It brought a new paradigm in the field with the development of Large Language Models (LLMs), such as BERT [51] and GPT [56], pre-trained on plain text and specialized on defined tasks. This new paradigm introduced a new way to perform prediction tasks in machine learning, in which instead of modelling directly the probability of an output label y given an input x , it provides for the modification of the input x using a template and prompting the LLM to fill it. The desired output y can be then extracted or inferred from the LLM's response [57]. A seminal work in this area has been proposed by [58], introducing a unified framework that converts text-based language problems into a text-to-text format.

The task of Question Answering (QA) has also been influenced by this new paradigm. [59], starting from the assumption that LLMs can learn relational knowledge in the same way they learn linguistic knowledge, proposed an approach to extract this knowledge using *fill-in-the-blank* cloze statements. This line of research paved the way for the development of models that use the latent representations of LLMs as knowledge bases [59] and use latent representations and knowledge bases in conjunction to approach knowledge-intensive tasks [60, 61]. However, the performance of the models on open-domain QA is still quite low [62].

A related and more general line of research in this context culminated with the development of conversational agents such as chatGPT [6]. These models can interact with humans and provide answers and solutions to different tasks prompted by the users. If, from one side, the popularity of this kind of models is increasing constantly, the research community has raised two main concerns to them. The first one is related to the LLMs' tendency to *hallucinate* [63] with the consequent generation of biased or harmful content [64]. The second concern regards the evaluation of chatGPT's performance due to the closed nature of this model and its continuous updates via Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (RLHF) [4] (see Section 3.3.1.1). If the first bias has social implications, the second may compromise a fair evaluation of the model. This is because it is not possible to assess if chatGPT has been contaminated, seeing during one of its training phases evaluation datasets. This problem has been demonstrated in other recent LLMs [65, 66].

To deepen these concerns, we propose a new evaluation based on specialist knowledge. We developed DYN-KNOWLEDGE v1.0, a new benchmark for QA based on information extracted from Wikipedia and related to non-popular entities in the music domain. In this way, we can test how reliable chatGPT is on very specific questions and a dataset that has never been published. However, it is important to notice that the questions in our benchmark are not impossible to answer. This is because we extracted questions and answers from Wikipedia, one of the most popular sources in NLP. We developed this evaluation inspired by the idea that LLMs have difficulties dealing with low-frequency entities and that if prompted with them, they are likely to *hallucinate*, producing fluent but unrealistic text. We compared the performance of chatGPT with a model that uses explicit knowledge representation in the form of Abstract Meaning Representation (AMR) [9] graphs to answer the questions. This explicit knowledge is structured as a Knowledge Graph (KG) [67] and thus can be queried. Such a structure also provides the source from which the answer was extracted, a desirable feature also for LLMs but difficult to obtain from them given that they are based on latent and not explicit representations.

The contributions of this section of the deliverable can be listed as follows:

- a new dynamic benchmark for open-format QA models;
- a new Knowledge Extraction pipeline based on explicit knowledge that can be used for QA;
- a systematic comparison between chatGPT and the explicit knowledge model centred on entity popularity.

3.2. Related Work

In this section, we first introduce recent works on the evaluation of chatGPT, then we present recent works about the use of AMR for knowledge extraction and QA. Also, we report upon recent approaches that blend latent and explicit knowledge representation to improve models' performance on QA tasks revolving around low frequency entities and long tail knowledge.

3.2.1. chatGPT evaluation

[68] proposed a systematic evaluation of chatGPT in NLP tasks covering 140 tasks, including QA, text summarization, code generation, and commonsense reasoning, and analyzing 255K responses. The results of this large-scale evaluation show that chatGPT can perform a wide variety of tasks with impressive performance. However, it is still far from achieving good performances in some tasks. A domain-specific evaluation of chatGPT was proposed by [69]. This evaluation centred on the biomedical domain and covered tasks such as relation extraction, document classification, QA, and summarization. The authors of this work found that chatGPT in a zero-shot setting can outperform fine-tuned generative models, such as BioGPT [70] and BioBART [71], only when the training set for the task is small. Otherwise, if the training set for fine-tuning is large, specialized models outperform chatGPT by a large margin.

A different evaluation aimed at checking how the predictions of chatGPT change over time was presented by [72]. The authors of this work used stance detection as a case in point and followed the experimental setting proposed in previous work by [73]. In this work were used publicly available data from SemEval 2016 Task 6 [74, 75] and P-stance [76]. The authors prompted chatGPT using, for each sentence in the dataset, the following template: *what's the attitude of the sentence: INPUT SENTENCE select from "favor, against or neutral"*. The evaluation shows big improvements comparing results from different time periods, highlighting the difficulty of evaluating this model that is continuously updated with unknown data. The authors concluded that a fair evaluation of this model should be novel in order to prevent test data leakage.

A common view in the literature is concerned with the closed nature of this model and with the high variability of the results that change substantially depending on apparently uncorrelated factors, such as the moment in which the model was used or a slight modification of the prompt. In such conditions, the parameters of the model, such as the temperature that controls the *creativity of the model*, are difficult to tune and adapt to the task at hand.

3.2.2. AMR for Knowledge Extraction and Question Answering

Graph-based semantic parsing has gained attention due to the potential of general-purpose representations, such as AMR. Text-to-AMR transduction based on neural machine translation and sequence-to-sequence (*seq2seq*) models achieved high performances (around 85% accuracy) both in English [26, 77], multilingual parsing [78, 79] and multi-formalisms scenarios [80].

Regarding information extraction end-tasks, [81] leveraged AMR semantic parsing for extracting information (molecular events/interactions) from biomedical documents, achieving promising results. With a similar objective (extracting fine-grained information from the biomedical scientific literature), [82] employed AMR to obtain an in-depth semantic structure of sentences and further enriched the resulting graphs with domain-specific information from external knowledge bases through edge-conditioned graph attention network (GAT, [83]). The fusion of the semantic structures uncovered by the AMR parsing and the highly specialist knowledge integrated from a domain-focused knowledge base brought tangible advantages for achieving high performances in the end-task goal.

[84] satisfactorily employed AMR as an intermediate logic for the semantic parsing of natural language to power a Knowledge Base Question Answering (KBQA) neuro-symbolic system. Similarly, [85] proved the advantages of employing the rich semantic representation offered by pre-trained AMR parsers to extract entities, relations, and events from unstructured sentences and encapsulate them into Information Networks through an encoder-decoder architecture. In [86], Commonsense QA is pursued considering the importance of representing the question's meaning

to predict the correct answer. The semantic parsing of the question is obtained by expanding an AMR graph with an external KG, which contains commonsense information (ConceptNet, [87]). The resulting graph is subsequently pruned to retain only the most informative knowledge to accomplish the task, then used to analyse the reasoning path and derive the correct answer. [84] proposes a Neuro-Symbolic Question Answering (NSQA) system, in which AMR parsing is used to understand questions, and the resulting AMR graph is mapped into query graphs (SPARQL queries) aligned with a Knowledge Base utilising deterministic mappings. [88] considers those deterministic mappings as prone to coverage and granularity mismatch and proposes a framework in which a transition-based semantic parser which integrates a BART-based model learns to transpile AMR into the SPARQL training language. [89] employs AMR-based modules (AMR parsing, AMR graph segmentation and AMR-To-Text generation) to better understand complex questions through question decomposition and achieve more interpretable multi-hop QA.

Nevertheless, the potential of AMR-based Knowledge Extraction and QA is hindered by the inherent difficulty in automatically retrieving the knowledge encoded in AMR graphs. In fact, crafting *ad hoc* structured queries can be complex and pose some accessibility barriers to non-technical users. The work described in this section of this thesis proposal aims to explore paths to combine the ease of querying that LLMs allow due to their ability to comprehend natural language queries with the reliability and granularity of detail that knowledge encoded in an AMR graph can provide.

3.2.3. Blending Latent and Explicit Knowledge Representation for Knowledge Extraction and Question Answering

Retrieval-augmented Language Models (LMs) leverage explicit knowledge gathered from external Knowledge Bases to mitigate hallucinations and improve performance on knowledge-intensive tasks. Such explicit knowledge is usually in the form of textual excerpts automatically retrieved from documental knowledge sources, as extensively reviewed in recent surveys [90], [91]. LMs performance increase in retrieval-augmented settings is particularly considerable when the knowledge to be elicited concerns low-frequency entities [7]. Exploiting structured information automatically extrapolated from a Knowledge Graphs bank to augment LMs is a less explored pathway, but recent studies shed light on the opportunities such a blend offers. [92] proposes RET-LLM, an infrastructure that provides LMs with a memory module, in which knowledge extracted from text in forms of triplets based on Davidsonian semantics [93] can be stored and successively retrieved. The authors claim that triplets prove especially beneficial in providing more precise and exhaustive output in QA settings when data aggregation is necessary. [94] introduces KnowledgeGPT, a framework in which LLMs are provided with an external symbolic Knowledge Base to store and retrieve knowledge to reply more comprehensively and accurately in complex QA tasks. The stored knowledge comprises information automatically extracted from text. [95] presents SUBgraph Retrieval-augmented GEneration (SURGE), in which they augment LLMs by leveraging the retrieval of relevant pieces of graphs from a more comprehensive Knowledge Graph to enable more factually consistent and knowledge-grounded dialogues. With similar objectives of enabling faithful QA, [96] introduces Chain-of-Knowledge (CoK), in which they augment LLMs by exploiting grounding information from external sources (both unstructured and structured) in a dynamic manner and encompassing a majority-consensus logic.

3.3. Methodology

In this section of the deliverable, we want to compare the performance of explicit and latent knowledge models on the QA task. To this end, we first collected a new benchmark for the task, and then we selected two representative models for both latent and explicit knowledge representation. The latent representation model is chatGPT. The explicit knowledge representation pipeline is the Polifonia Knowledge Extractor (PKE)¹, the fulcrum of which is [13, Text2AMR2FRED], that produces graph-based semantic representations of the textual evidence we employed for the QA task. [13, Text2AMR2FRED] transforms text into RDF/OWL Knowledge Graphs that follow [12, FRED] knowledge

¹<https://github.com/polifonia-project/Polifonia-Knowledge-Extractor>

patterns. The tool leverages Abstract Meaning Representation (AMR) [9] as an intermediate semantic formalism. In the following sections, we describe the models and then the dataset.

Table 3.1: Coreference resolution and replacements correctness in a sample of sentences extrapolated from Wikipedia.

mention type	#incorrect	#correct	Total
third-person personal pronouns	4(8%)	48(92%)	52(100%)

Table 3.2: Example of data collection for the named entity corresponding to the Wikipedia page *Teresina_Brambilla*, *Giuseppina_Ronzi_de_Begnisi* and *Wolfgang_Amadeus_Mozart*. ID column reports the sample's unique identifier in DYNACKNOWLEDGE v1.0 to facilitate the reader in retrieving the sample in the benchmark.

ID	Gender	Analyst's Question	Analyst's Answer	Sentence from Wikipedia containing the answer
18	F	How long was Teresina Brambilla's career as a musician?	25 years	Teresa "Teresina" Brambilla (15 April 1845 – 1 July 1921) was an Italian soprano who sang in the major opera houses of Europe in a career spanning 25 years.
41	F	Which female colleague did Giuseppina Ronzi de Begnisi argue with during the rehearsals of Maria Stuarda?	Anna Del Sere	Ronzi was also known for her capricious attitudes and for having confrontations and arguments with female colleagues, including the famous altercation with Anna Del Sere during the rehearsals of Maria Stuarda.
5	M	How old was Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart when he started to compose?	5 years old	Already competent on keyboard and violin, he composed from the age of five and performed before European royalty.

3.3.1. Models

3.3.1.1. chatGPT

As far as it is known, chatGPT is trained in a three-step process [6]. First, an initial LLM based on GPT 3/3.5 [4] is fine-tuned on a dataset created by asking human annotators to write what is the desired output to prompts submitted to the OpenAI API. The next phase consists of sampling a set of prompts from a larger collection of prompts submitted to the OpenAI API. For each of them, the LLM produces multiple responses that are then ranked by human annotators. With this information starts the second training phase in which a reward model (RM) is learned on the response-ranking task using the reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF) mechanism [4]. This step keeps the LLM frozen and solely trains the RM. In the last training step, the LLM is used to generate responses to a new set of prompts not included in the previous steps. In this phase, the now-frozen reward model is used as a reward function, and the LLM is further fine-tuned to maximize this reward using the Proximal Policy Optimization algorithm [97].

3.3.1.2. Polifonia Knowledge Extractor

The Polifonia Knowledge Extractor (PKE)² is a framework for extracting knowledge from contemporary and historical texts. Its fulcrum is [13, Text2AMR2FRED], a tool that relies on AMR parsing for extracting knowledge from unstructured text. AMR formalism is grounded in PropBank's *Frames* [98], which constitute the core lexicon of this resource. Frames consist of predicate-argument structures named *rolesets*. AMR can be expressed by using the PENMAN

²<https://github.com/polifonia-project/Polifonia-Knowledge-Extractor>¹⁶

Figure 3.1: Text2AMR2FRED pipeline schema.

serialisation format [99], a notation convention that enables encoding the semantic dependencies of directed and rooted graphs such as AMR graphs. In [13, Text2AMR2FRED] framework, depicted in Figure 3.1, AMR graphs serve as an event-centric representation of an input text, well-suited for retrieving the essential elements of a situation described in one or multiple sentences. For example, the ARG0 of the PropBank predicate SING-01 encodes information about the singer (an *agent* in an act of singing). The advantage of AMR representation is detaching from syntax variability and word forms, providing the same graph for sentences conveying almost the same meaning with a different syntactic or lexical realisation. [13, Text2AMR2FRED] framework extracts information from the text and stores it in AMR graphs, then it exploits the [10, AMR2FRED] tool to transform AMR graphs into OWL-compliant RDF KGs, following FRED’s formal knowledge patterns. Additional relevant knowledge missing in the text (e.g., common sense knowledge) can be recovered from other KBs such as those contained in Framester [100] Semantic Hub.

3.3.1.2.1. Implementation details In the Polifonia Knowledge Extractor framework, we implement techniques for minimising the loss of information in the source text, such as coreference resolution, i.e., the task of clustering spans of text (*mentions*) that correspond to the same single entity (*referent*). For our experiments, we used the model proposed by [101] and applied referent substitutions only to a subset of pronominal mentions, the third-person personal pronouns. As we report in Table 3.1, we evaluated the substitutions performed, achieving a 92% accuracy on a set of 52 third-person pronominal mentions occurring in a sample of sentences extrapolated from Wikipedia. The text2AMR parsing module of our Knowledge Extraction framework relies on a neural semantic parser, i.e., SPRING [26]³, which allows us to perform the AMR2text task with the same model. This model exploits BLINK [14] to link named entities to their unique entry in Wikipedia (*wikification*).

As a last step, our Knowledge Extraction framework includes [10, AMR2FRED], a tool that transforms AMR graphs

³<https://github.com/SapienzaNLP/spring>

into RDF/OWL KGs that follow [12, FRED] machine reader's theoretical model. The resulting KGs are further enriched with knowledge from external Knowledge Bases (KBs) through Framester [102], a semantic resources hub, which enriches the KGs with, for example, Word Sense Disambiguation (WSD) information based on the RDF version of WordNet [103], included in Framester.

3.3.2. DYNACKNOWLEDGE v1.0: a new Dynamic Benchmark for Knowledge Extraction

With this deliverable, we introduce DYNACKNOWLEDGE v1.0, a new manually curated dataset for open-form QA made of questions based on the Wikipedia pages of historical entities picked from the Periodicals module of the Polifonia Textual Corpus, whose publication dates range from 1823 to 1900. The dataset comprises 82 samples (question, answer, textual evidence tuples). The textual evidence element consists of the Wikipedia page sentences containing the answer to the question. Given the nature of the corpus, the selected historical characters are domain-specific (music) and known to be active or alive before the periodicals' publication dates range. We maintained a 50-50 gender distribution between the selected named entities⁴. As a result, half of the questions focus on male historical characters and the other half on female historical characters. We choose to create our benchmark following this composition centred on the person named entities' gender distribution because, in investigating to what extent named entities' popularity influence chatGPT's capability to answer factual questions correctly, we also want to understand how much we can trust chatGPT when we ask questions about named entities of different gender as a consequence of lower or higher popularity. DYNACKNOWLEDGE v1.0 is intended to be dynamic and updated over time with new samples always related to low-frequency entities.

3.3.2.1. Data collection

Data collection was performed by Foreign Languages and Literature undergraduate students who received *ad hoc* training as part of their bachelor's degree curricular internship. They recorded the data in a spreadsheet following the format as in the sample reported in Table 3.2. On a more nuanced level, the analysts (i) selected a historical character (technically, a named entity of type PERSON) occurring in a corpus of music historical periodicals; (ii) accessed the chosen historical character's Wikipedia page and selected one or more sentences reporting a fact relating to the entity; (iii) formulated a question related to the historical character, answerable by the selected Wikipedia page sentences.

For each sample, we report the following information:

1. ID: the sample unique identifier;
2. DATE: the date, or range of dates, on which the sample was collected;
3. WIKIPEDIA PAGE: the Wikipedia page of the sample's named entity;
4. GENDER: the gender of the sample's named entity;
5. QUESTION: the question about a fact concerning the sample's named entity;
6. PROMPT: the prompt submitted to chatGPT, containing the question;
7. ANSWER: the ground truth answer;
8. PROVENANCE: the textual evidence, i.e. the sentence(s) from the entity's Wikipedia page containing the answer to the question.

⁴In our study, we restrict to binary gender categories, which, although not reflecting real-world diversity, lets us move the first steps towards the definition of our method. We consider a *female* person named entity a historical character that is referred to, in its Wikipedia page, with the pronoun *she*, a *male* person named entity a historical figure who is referred to, in its Wikipedia page, with the pronoun *he*.

Figure 3.2: AMR subgraph containing the answer to the question "How long was Teresina Brambilla career as a musician?".

3.4. Experimental setup

Figure 3.3: Process followed by the analysts to record the AMR graph's *answerability* assessment. *Answerability* is defined in 3.4.1.2. If *answerability* is satisfied, the analysts extract the subgraph containing the answer to the question that is then transformed into text via AMR2text to confirm the AMR graph's *answerability*. If not, they explain the error observed in the graph.

We tested GPT-3.5 (Default) model, accessed via its free online version (ChatGPT⁵ and our Knowledge Extraction pipeline (cfr. 3.3.1.2). We designed and executed the experiments from August 4th to August 22nd, 2023. At that time, it was not possible for a user to fine-tune GPT-3.5 (Default) model. Therefore, we evaluated it in a zero-shot setting. We tested GPT-3.5 (Default) and our Knowledge Extraction pipeline on the same questions formulated and collected in the data collection phase (cfr. 3.3.2.1). We compared the free text answers to the questions returned by chatGPT and the AMR graphs produced by parsing, with our Knowledge Extraction pipeline, the Wikipedia sentences containing the answer to the question.

⁵<https://chat.openai.com/>

Table 3.3: Evaluation - chatGPT's answer assessment. ID column reports the sample's unique identifier in DYNACKNOWLEDGE v1.0.

ID	Evaluator's Prompt	chatGPT's answer	Assessment
18	How long was Teresina Brambilla's career as a musician? Give a straight answer.	As of my last knowledge update in September 2021, there is no widely known or documented musician by the name of Teresina Brambilla in the public domain. Therefore, I cannot provide information about the length of her musical career. It's possible that she gained recognition after my last update or that she is not a prominent figure in the music world.	Not given
41	Which female colleague did Giuseppina Ronzi de Begnis argue with during the rehearsals of Maria Stuarda? Give a straight answer.	Giuseppina Ronzi de Begnis argued with Maria Malibran during the rehearsals of Maria Stuarda.	No
5	How old was Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart when he started to compose? Give a straight answer.	Wolfgang Amadeus Mozart started composing at the age of 5.	Yes

3.4.1. Zero-context prompting

To perform the evaluation, the analysts had to compare chatGPT's answers to the questions and AMR graph's *answerability*. The evaluation was performed by the same interns who conducted the data collection, with the support of the authors of this deliverable for the AMR graph *answerability* assessment.

3.4.1.1. ChatGPT answer assessment

To assess chatGPT's answer, the analysts had to submit the questions as prompts to the free online version of chatGPT and assess the answer returned by chatGPT. They recorded the results by adding the following information to the dataset described at 3.3.2:

1. CHATGPT ANSWER: chatGPT's answer;
2. CHATGPT ANSWER ASSESSMENT (YES/NO/NOT GIVEN): manual evaluation of whether the chatGPT response is correct ("yes"), incorrect ("no"), or the model does not give any answers ("not given").

Example In the example reported in Table 3.3, chatGPT's answer has been assessed as *not given*. In fact, chatGPT replies to the prompt stating that, to the best of its knowledge, there is no known musician named *Teresina Brambilla*, and for this reason, it cannot answer the question asked (namely, returning information about the length of her career).

3.4.1.2. AMR graph answerability

To ensure a fair evaluation, we manually checked the AMR graphs to assess AMR graphs' *answerability*. The process is depicted in Figure 3.3. The analysts transformed the Wikipedia sentences containing the answer to the question into an AMR graph via our Knowledge Extraction framework and then assessed the *answerability* of the AMR graph. We define *answerability* as the ability of the AMR graph to encode the information needed to answer a question. It is satisfied when the AMR graph contains a subgraph that correctly captures the information needed to answer a question. The subgraph must report the semantically correct PropBank predicates, their core roles (arguments), and non-core roles (relations) structure. It must be possible to translate the subgraph back to text using an AMR2text model and obtain a natural language sentence containing an answer to the question. They recorded the AMR graphs' answerability assessment results by adding the following information to the dataset described at 3.3.2:

1. AMR GRAPH (PENMAN): the AMR graph corresponding to the PROVENANCE (cfr. 3.3.2.1);
2. AMR GRAPH'S ANSWERABILITY (YES/NO/NOT GIVEN): manual assessment of the *answerability* of the AMR graph;
3. IF SO, WHICH IS THE SUB-GRAPH CONTAINING THE ANSWER?: the AMR sub-graph containing the answer to the question;

4. AMR GRAPH'S ERROR DESCRIPTION: if the value reported in DOES THE AMR GRAPH CONTAIN AN ANSWER TO THE QUESTION? is "no", an explanation of the error observed.

3.4.1.3. Metrics

We started from the assumption that finding the most suitable metrics for QA is a difficult task and that a metric such as BLEU [104], ROUGE [105] or METEOR [106] can alter the evaluation of free-form QA [107]. With this in mind, as we presented in the previous section, we manually checked the answers of the two models under analysis to not bias the results. With the answers manually checked and divided into the canonical *correct*, *wrong*, and *not given*, we are able to compute standard precision (P), recall (R) and F1 (F1) as:

$$P = \frac{\text{correct}}{|\text{samples}|}, R = \frac{\text{correct}}{|\text{samples}| - \text{not given}},$$

and

$$F1 = \frac{2 * P * R}{P + R}.$$

3.4.2. Context-augmented prompting

In this Sub-section, we describe the experiments that we carried out to combine the capabilities of both the latent and explicit knowledge representation models in a single framework in line with retrieval-augmented generative models [60].

Following [7], we evaluate whether ChatGPT answers' correctness can improve if the prompt is augmented with context. We experiment with three context types:

1. EVIDENCE SPAN: we extend the prompt by adding the PROVENANCE, namely the textual evidence, i.e. the sentence(s) from the entity's Wikipedia page containing the answer to the question (cfr. 3.3.2.1) and asking ChatGPT to answer the question considering the information contained in the provenance;
2. AMR GRAPH: we extend the prompt by adding the AMR GRAPH (PENMAN) corresponding to the provenance (see 3.4.1.2). We ask ChatGPT to act as an expert in Abstract Meaning Representation graphs and answer the question considering the information in the AMR graph obtained from the provenance.
3. RDF/OWL KNOWLEDGE GRAPH (N-TRIPLES): we extend the prompt by adding the RDF/OWL KNOWLEDGE GRAPH corresponding to the provenance, obtained with [13, Text2AMR2FRED]. We ask ChatGPT to act as an expert in RDF/OWL Knowledge Graphs and answer the question considering the information in the RDF/OWL KG obtained from the provenance.

Examples of the prompts experimented in this setting are reported in Appendix C.

Table 3.4: ChatGPT's answers and AMR graphs' answerability assessment reported as precision (P), recall (R), f1-measure (F1) dividing the questions according to the gender of the named entity involved, female (F) and male (M).

NE's gender	chatGPT			AMR		
	P	R	F1	P	R	F1
F	0,22	0,31	0,26	0,51	0,51	0,51
M	0,54	0,58	0,56	0,49	0,50	0,49
Total	0,38	0,46	0,42	0,50	0,50	0,50

3.5. Results and Analysis

3.5.1. Zero-context prompting

Table 3.4 compares chatGPT answers and the AMR graphs' answerability assessment. The table shows that the AMR graphs effectively capture the answers to the questions 50% of the times, while chatGPT's answer is correct 38% of the times (precision). We can also see that the recall of chatGPT is higher than precision. ChatGPT, in fact, can give an answer that indicates that it is not able to provide information. On the other hand, with AMR parsing, this is not possible. We considered a question prompted to AMR as *not given* only if the parser cannot produce a graph. This happened just one time in our experiments.

Table 3.5: The WikiData identifier (QID) average frequency and standard deviation distribution across the named entities of our sample, split per gender and chatGPT answers'/AMR graphs' answerability assessment

NE's gender	chatGPT answer						AMR graph answerability						#Total	
	#yes		#no		#not given		#yes		#no		#not given			
	Avg	StdDev	Avg	StdDev	Avg	StdDev	Avg	StdDev	Avg	StdDev	Avg	StdDev	Avg	StdDev
F	76	126	37	93	4	2	42	96	31,5	85,5	N/A	N/A	37	90
M	910	1606	215	618	6	3	817	1661	356	755	61	N/A	573	1279
All	660	1391	113	413	5	3	410	1197	194	555	61	N/A	302	935

In the example with ID 18 reported in Table 3.3, chatGPT's answer has been assessed as *not given*. In fact, chatGPT replies to the prompt stating that, to the best of its knowledge, there is no known musician named *Teresina Brambilla*, and for this reason, it cannot answer the question asked ("*How long was Teresina Brambilla's career as a musician?*"). But, as recorded in Table 3.2, the sentence from Wikipedia containing the answer (PROVENANCE) collected for this sample states that the correct answer for the sample's question is *25 years*. In the example with ID 41 reported in Table 3.3, chatGPT's answer assessment is *no*, meaning that the answer given by chatGPT is not correct. In fact, as recorded in Table 3.2, the sentence from Wikipedia containing the answer (PROVENANCE) collected for this sample reports that the correct answer for the sample's question ("*Which female colleague did Giuseppina Ronzi de Begnis argue with during the rehearsals of Maria Stuarda?*") is *Anna Del Sere*, while chatGPT mentions an argument between Giuseppina Ronzi and Maria Malibrán. In the example with ID 5 reported in Table 3.3, chatGPT's answer assessment is *yes*. chatGPT's answer correctness is easily verifiable by comparing chatGPT's answer in Table 3.3 with the analyst's answer reported in Table 3.2: both contain the same piece of knowledge, namely that Mozart started composing at the age of five.

Figure 3.2 reports the AMR subgraph containing the answer to the question formulated for the sample with ID 18 (cfr. Table 3.2). The subgraph, extrapolated from the AMR graph resulting from the text2AMR parsing of the PROVENANCE (sentence from Wikipedia containing the answer) of the same sample is considered able to answer the question. It has a *root node*, z0/SOPRANO, that is linked to the *instance node* z1/PERSON by the *non-core role* :DOMAIN. This triple correctly reflects the "*named-entity-is-noun*" semantics. The *instance node* z1/PERSON is linked to the *instance node* z2/NAME by the *non-core role* :NAME. This triple correctly states that the *instance node* z1/PERSON has a *name*, therefore is a *named entity*. It branches out in three leaves nodes linked by the relation :OP, which reports the three tokens of the sentence that make up the named entity mention (*Teresa*, "*Teresina*", *Brambilla*). The *instance node* z1/PERSON is also linked to the PropBank *predicate node* z8/SING-01 by the *inverse core role* :ARG0-OF. This triple correctly captures the semantics of relative clauses. SING-01 is also linked to the node z14/CAREER by the *non-core role* :DURATION, which is itself linked through the same relation to the *instance node* z15/temporal-quantity, which captures the semantics of a specific type of quantity. It branches out into the two tokens of the sentence that make up the temporal quantity mention by its arguments :UNIT (z16/year) and :QUANT (25).

The rich semantic structure of this subgraph encloses all the elements required to answer the question asked, as can also be verified by transforming the AMR graph back to text employing the same model used for Text2AMR,

i.e., SPRING. The resulting natural language sentence *Teresa Teresina Brambilla is a soprano who has sung for a 25-year career* answers correctly the question asked (cfr. the column *Analyst's Answer* in Table 3.3).

In the AMR graph resulting from the text2AMR transformation of the sentence from Wikipedia containing the answer (PROVENANCE) of the sample with ID 41, the named entity *Maria Stuarda* is incorrectly classified as a PERSON instead of as a WORK-OF-ART:

```
(z16 / person
  :name (z17 / name
    :op1 "Maria"
    :op2 "Stuarda"))
```

The named entity classification reported in the example above compromises the correctness of the resulting AMR graph⁶. The AMR graph *answerability* criteria is not satisfied.

3.5.1.1. Issues

While assessing AMR graphs' *answerability*, we encountered two main issues.

3.5.1.1.1. Coreference resolution. Some of the sentences collected from Wikipedia pages (cfr. 3.3.2.1) contain only mentions of the entity and not the entity's referent. Mentions can be *personal pronouns* (as in the sentence *"He composed from a very young age, first studying with his uncle Giovanni Mazzetti and later with Luigi Caruso in Perugia"*), *possessive pronouns* (as in the sentence *"His parents were John Reeves, a musician of Yorkshire origin, and his wife, Rosina"*), *names* (i.e., proper nouns in their shortened forms, as in the sentence *"Barnby was born at York, as a son of Thomas Barnby, who was an organist"*). As reported in paragraph 3.3.1.2, in our Knowledge Extraction framework, we apply coreference resolution to only a subset of pronominal mentions (the third-person personal pronouns). As a consequence, AMR subgraphs extrapolated from sentences in which the only mention of the entity is a possessive pronoun or a surname are never assessed as correct because, at present, we do not manage them in our Knowledge Extraction framework. Instead, we considered AMR subgraphs extrapolated from sentences in which the only reference to the entity was a third-person personal pronoun as correct when they corresponded to our *answerability* criteria.

3.5.1.1.2. Wikification In assessing AMR graphs *answerability*, we do not assess the correctness of the entity linking information. Still, we focus on the correct recognition of the entity mention and on its correct classification to a pre-defined entity type⁷. This is because, in our particular case, we are using Wikipedia documents from which it is possible to extract unambiguous entity references disposing of entity linking altogether.

3.5.1.2. Popularity and gender effect

Looking at the results in Table 3.4 in a more granular way, we can see that chatGPT tends to return wrong answers more often when prompted with questions about female historical characters. This observation might corroborate the hypotheses regarding gender and popularity biases in LLMs [108] and in KBs such as Wikipedia [109]. We wanted to verify whether the named entities' WikiData identifier (QID) frequency influenced the results. Therefore, we added the following two pieces of information to the benchmark described in 3.3.2:

1. QID: The QID corresponding to the sample's named entity Wikipedia page;
2. QID_FREQUENCY: number of times an internal link in Wikipedia⁸ can be mapped to a QID.

⁶All samples' full AMR graphs can be found in the spreadsheet at https://github.com/polifonia-project/llms-vs-specialised-knowledge/blob/main/data/DynaKnowledge_v1.0_280224.xlsx

⁷Entity types list (<https://www.isi.edu/~ulf/amr/lib/ne-types.html>) and criteria for their assignation are defined in AMR annotation guidance instructions.

⁸We used the `enwiki-20220120` dump.

As we can see in Table 3.5, chatGPT’s capacity of returning correct answers appears to be influenced by the frequency of the named entities: male named entities have, in our dataset, an average QID frequency of 573 against 37 of the female named entities, and chatGPT’s answer is correct 22% of the times when prompted with questions regarding female named entities, and 54% of the times when prompted with questions regarding male named entities. Suppose we focus on the sub-sample of cases in which chatGPT returns the highest number of correct answers. Those cases correspond to male historical characters with the highest QID frequency average across the whole sample (910).

We calculated the correlation between chatGPT’s answers’ correctness and the popularity of the named entities using Spearman’s Rho coefficient. The result obtained (Spearman’s Rho = 0.48084) shows a positive correlation. On the other hand, we calculated the correlation between AMR graphs’ answerability and the popularity of the named entities using the same coefficient, and the results obtained (Spearman’s Rho = −0.06758) demonstrate a negligible correlation between the two variables. This confirms the hypothesis that we raise, namely that our more simple knowledge extraction pipeline is more robust to entities’ popularity variation than a LLM such as chatGPT. To consolidate this result, we repeat the same analysis between chatGPT’s answers/AMR graphs’ answerability and the gender of the named entities, obtaining the same result (Spearman’s Rho = 0.32, namely low but positive correlation for chatGPT, and Spearman’s Rho = −0,02, namely no correlation for our knowledge extraction pipeline). These findings might strengthen recent findings about popularity bias in LLMs reported by [15] and LLMs’ struggle with long-tail knowledge investigated by [5]. Notably, the AMR graphs’ *answerability* is apparently robust to any major bias toward the gender or the QID frequency of the entities involved.

Notably, the AMR graphs’ *answerability* is apparently robust to any major bias toward the gender or the QID frequency of the entities involved.

3.5.2. Context-augmented Prompting

Table 3.6: Context-augmented Prompting.

Model	Prompt	Context Type	P	R	F1
ChatGPT (3.5)	Zero-context	-	0,38	0,46	0,42
gpt-3.5-turbo-16k	Augmented prompting	Evidence Span	0,97	0,97	0,97
		AMR graph	0,85	0,85	0,85
		RDF/OWL KG	0,66	0,86	0,75

We explored the application of context-augmented prompting as detailed in Sub-section 3.4.2. The ensuing Table 3.6 presents the outcomes we obtained. It is important to note that the context for augmentation was manually chosen and not automatically retrieved.

An inspection of the table reveals that the enhancement of prompts with context invariably leads to improved results, irrespective of the type of context being the evidence span, the Abstract Meaning Representations (AMR) derived from the evidence span, or the RDF/OWL KG obtained from the evidence span. The maximum F1 score was achieved by augmenting the prompt with the textual evidence span.

However, we acknowledge that obtaining the correct text for context augmentation is difficult in a fully automated RAG framework. In this regard, it is plausible that augmenting the context with AMR or RDF subgraphs, automatically retrieved from a large graph bank, could yield higher F1 scores than using extracted text. Further investigation into these possibilities would provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of AMR and RDF in enhancing LLMs-based QA tasks.

To expand upon the potential benefits of AMR and RDF, it is worth noting their respective strengths. AMRs offer a semantic representation of the relationship between concepts within a sentence or a set of sentences. This representation can be particularly useful when dealing with complex queries that require a deep understanding of the underlying meaning.

On the other hand, RDF and OWL knowledge graphs provide a more structured and comprehensive representation of real-world entities and their relationships. They are particularly valuable in scenarios where large amounts of data need to be processed and integrated, such as in information retrieval systems or QA applications that involve multiple sources of information.

In conclusion, our results suggest that context-augmented prompting can significantly improve the performance for low-frequency. However, further research is required to fully understand the potential benefits of using AMRs and RDF/OWL knowledge graphs as alternatives or complements to textual context for augmentation.

3.6. Conclusion

In this section of the deliverable, we conducted an evaluation of explicit and latent knowledge representation models. This evaluation was possible thanks to the development and release of DYNACKNOWLEDGE v1.0, a new benchmark for the open-form QA task. This first release serves as a starting point for developing a dynamic benchmark that will outlive the project, being updated over time to tackle the continuous improvements that current LLMs are having. The results of our experiments show that our benchmark is particularly challenging. In particular, we found that chatGPT struggles to answer questions related to low-frequency entities. This result was accompanied by the assessment of the better performances of a simple knowledge extraction model. This model demonstrated to be more robust on the variation of the frequencies of entities around which the questions of DYNACKNOWLEDGE v1.0 have been formulated.

The way in which we want to continue populating the benchmark is dynamic, aligning with current trends in benchmarking NLP models [110]. We believe that it is necessary since models like chatGPT are continuously updated, and also considering that an answer from these models can vary over time or by slightly changing the prompt. This will allow us to examine further the interplay between gender and popularity biases and to deepen the investigation regarding the difficulties that LLMs demonstrate when dealing with long-tail knowledge [5].

For the zero-context prompting (cfr. 3.5.1), we plan to transform the AMR graphs that our Knowledge Extraction pipeline outputs into Resource Description Framework (RDF) KGs. This will allow us to automate the comparative evaluation through structured interrogations and develop an automatic evaluation metric.

For the context-augmented prompting, we aim to automate the retrieval of the context used to augment the prompt. For the evidence span-augmented prompting, we will experiment with the most established frameworks for retrieval-augmented generation. The AMR graph- and the RDF/OWL KG-augmented prompting are less explored pathways, and we aim to tackle them building on top of the AMR for Knowledge Extraction and QA approaches described in Sub-section 3.2.2.

3.7. Software and Data Release

We collect in this subsection the main software and data resources mentioned in Section 3 of this deliverable. Details about their compliance with the FAIR protocol are reported in Chapter 4 of this report.

- DYNACKNOWLEDGE v1.0 and the evaluation results can be found at: <https://github.com/polifonia-project/llms-vs-specialised-knowledge>.

4. FAIR Protocol

We have implemented a number of actions to ensure that these outputs are in compliance with the FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship [111]. The outputs released as a result of the work described in this deliverable (all code, data, and related resources), summarised in Section 4.1 of this Chapter, are available online at their respective GitHub repositories. The latest versions of the outputs are available on Zenodo, in synchronisation with GitHub releases for consistent versioning. Via GitHub and Zenodo, the outputs have a unique and persistent identifier and is registered in a searchable source.

4.1. Overall Software and Data Release Summary for FAIR Protocol Section

- **Historical Entity Linking** (cfr. Chapter 2 of this deliverable):
 - MHERCL v1.0 and ELD - Available at <https://github.com/polifonia-project/historical-entity-linking>. Its persistent URI (DOI) is 10.5281/zenodo.10721804¹.
- **Evaluation of knowledge extraction methods through QA** (cfr. Chapter 3 of this Deliverable):
 - DYNACKNOWLEDGE and the evaluation results - Available at <https://github.com/polifonia-project/llms-vs-specialised-knowledge>. Its persistent URI (DOI) is 10.5281/zenodo.8396416².

Through the addition of YAML metadata according to the Polifonia Ecosystem rulebook³, all outputs are also integrated within the Ecosystem automatically through its future releases with well-described, machine-processable metadata from various interoperable schemas. Furthermore, being integrated as part of the Polifonia Ecosystem, all data and metadata produced use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.

Licensing. All the outputs presented in this deliverable follow the guidelines and the recommendations in the Polifonia Data Management Plan. All outputs listed in Section 4.1 of this Chapter are made available under CC-BY 4.0.

Sustainability and preservation plan. All outputs listed in Section 4.1 of this Chapter is under version control on public GitHub repositories (c.f. Section 4.1 of this Chapter), and all repositories are also published on Zenodo (with associated DOIs). The storage of all resources on GitHub guarantees their persistence beyond the project.

Documentation. While improving and extending our contributions, we have also invested efforts on producing high quality documentation for our resources. Each software and data release GitHub repository created for this deliverable has a clear and well-structured README where all the preliminary information that are necessary to understand the domain and the goals of the outputs are provided upfront.

¹<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10721804>

²<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10723077>

³<https://github.com/polifonia-project/rulebook>

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A. Appendix A

A.1. Named Entities Classification in MHERCL v1.0

A.1.1. Named Entities Types

The types assigned to Named Entities (NEs) in MHERCL v1.0 are selected from the AMR named entity types list¹. We report them in the bullet list below:

- person, family, animal, language, nationality, ethnic-group, regional-group, religious-group, political-movement
- organization, company, government-organization, military, criminal-organization, political-party, market-sector school, university, research-institute, team, league
- location, city, city-district, county, state, province, territory, country, local-region, country-region, world-region, continent
- ocean, sea, lake, river, gulf, bay, strait, canal peninsula, mountain, volcano, valley, canyon, island, desert, forest, moon, planet, star, constellation
- facility, airport, station, port, tunnel, bridge, road, railway-line, canal building, theater, museum, palace, hotel, worship-place, sports-facility, market, park, zoo, amusement-park
- event, incident, natural-disaster, earthquake, war, conference, game, festival
- product, vehicle, ship, aircraft, aircraft-type, spaceship, car-make, work-of-art, picture, music, show, broadcast-program
- publication, book, newspaper, magazine, journal
- natural-object
- award, law, court-decision, treaty, music-key², musical-note², food-dish, writing-script, variable, program

In Table A.1, we report all the entity types assigned to NEs in MHERCL v1.0.

A.1.2. Named Entities Types Taxonomy

As described in paragraph 2.6.2 of this report, the gold NER class (*type*) is used in the functionality that assesses the plausibility of the candidates according to their types. To optimize such filter, we developed a taxonomy categorizing each named entity types occurring in MHERCL v1.0 into a hierarchy of types. When applying the type filter functionality, we expanded the dataset's gold type for each entity by including their more generic types from this taxonomy. The taxonomy is reported below:

- B-event
 - B-concert
 - B-festival
- B-facility
 - B-street
 - B-road
 - B-park
- B-building

¹<https://www.isi.edu/~ulf/amr/lib/ne-types.html>

²We decided not to annotate music-key and musical-notes as entities because they do not correspond to real-world things indicating a unique individual

- B-theatre
- B-university
- B-worship-place
- B-museum
- B-college
- B-company
- B-school
- B-hall
- B-language
- B-organization
 - B-theatre
 - B-university
 - B-worship-place
 - B-museum
 - B-college
 - B-company
 - B-school
 - B-empire
 - B-government-organization
 - B-religious-group
 - B-band
- B-person
- B-publication
 - B-book
 - B-magazine
 - B-newspaper
 - B-journal
- B-work-of-art
 - B-music
 - B-opera
 - B-symphony
 - B-book
 - B-song
- B-location
 - B-park
 - B-hall
 - B-city
 - B-city-district
 - B-continent
 - B-country
 - B-county
 - B-local-region
 - B-mountain
 - B-road
 - B-square
 - B-country-region
 - B-province
 - B-island

Table A.1: Named entity types occurring in MHERCL v1.0

named entity type	#occurrences
person	1253
city	251
music	188
organization	94
work-of-art	85
country	78
building	52
opera	52
theatre	41
worship-place	41
publication	26
book	24
road	24
company	16
school	16
city-district	13
magazine	9
event	8
festival	8
street	7
mountain	6
university	6
government-organization	5
college	4
facility	4
local-region	4
county	4
continent	4
journal	3
square	3
song	3
concert	3
location	3
river	3
museum	3
newspaper	3
country-region	3
symphony	2
religious-group	2
thing	2
person	2
family	2
language	1
band	1
province	1
island	1
park	1
empire	1
hotel	1
scholarship	1
institution	1
village	1
town	1
books	1
person (fictional character)	1
lake	1
hall	1
resistor	1

B. Appendix B

B.1. Annotation Guidelines for the Musical Heritage Historical named Entities Recognition, Classification and Linking benchmark (MHERCL v1.0)

B.1.1. Annotation Tool

- We developed and used an *ad hoc* tool, available on the Web, specifically designed for serving a two-fold purpose: 1. annotating and linking Named Entities (NEs) occurring in the *Periodicals* module of the PTC¹⁵; 2. assessing the correctness of NEs recognition, classification (NERC) and Entity Linking (EL) performed off-the-shelf by the text2AMR step of the [13, Text2AMR2FRED] module. As extensively reported in chapter 2 of this report, in the text2AMR step of Text2AMR2FRED, NEs recognition and classification is performed by SPRING [26] and EL by BLINK [14]. The tool will be described in this Appendix by reporting screenshots.

B.1.1.1. Note on Annotations Tool Screenshots and Examples

- To illustrate the full range of annotation tool functionalities, screenshots and examples may intentionally include incorrect predictions by SPRING [26] and BLINK [14] of named entity recognition, classification, and linking. These are included to provide a comprehensive overview of how the tool allows the annotators to enter a rich annotation input in the Annotation Tool.

B.2. Named Entity Recognition (NER) and Entity Linking (EL) Annotation Guidelines

B.2.1. Named Entity Recognition (NER)

Figure B.1: NLP pipeline introduction for the annotators of MHERCL v1.0.

B.2.1.1. General guidelines

- The annotators were instructed to consider a named entity a real-world thing indicating a unique individual through a proper noun [17]. The annotators were given a brief introduction to a typical NLP pipeline (tokenization, part-of-speech tagging, word sense disambiguation, named entities recognition and entity linking), with special emphasis on the Named Entities Recognition (NER) and Entity Linking (EL) tasks. In Figure B.1, we can see the slide used to support these general guidelines for the annotators.
- *Nested entities*. The annotators were instructed not to annotate nested NE. In cases such as *Account of the Oxford Commemoration Concerts*, the only valid named entity would be the "main" one (in our example, the entity of type PUBLICATION *Account of the Oxford Commemoration Concerts*). Therefore, in our example, "Oxford" would not be annotated as an entity of type CITY.

B.2.1.2. Example in the Annotation Tool

Sentence #47 (BLEURT: 1) Dwight's Journal of Music_1855-002_ms_1

And in the beautiful galleries of the Prince Es sterhdzy, (that munificent patron | of: Art) one can, at least, recall in imagination some- strains of the choice chamber music. of, Beethoven, to which their walls echoed in the presence of the great master, and in his palmist days. os se I was much impressed by the fine monument of the Archduchess Christina, by Canova, which stands in the Church of the Augustines.

The image shows a screenshot of an annotation tool interface. On the left, there is a complex parse tree for the sentence. On the right, a panel titled "Named entities" displays a detected entity: "z13 person (Prince Es sterhdzy)". Below this, it shows the "Entity mention: Prince Es sterhdzy" and a "This is" section with a green "Correct" button and a red "Wrong" button. There are two input fields for "Entity name or mention": one without OCR errors (containing "Prince Esterházy") and one with OCR errors (containing "Prince Es sterhdzy").

Figure B.2: NER - Example in the Annotation Tool

- As we can see in Figure B.2, the annotator can assess whether the NER performed off-the-shelf by the text2AMR parser [26] employed in [13, Text2AMR2FRED] is correct or not. If it is incorrect (as in the case of the Figure), the annotator is requested to record the NE superficial mention with and without OCR errors. This strategy has allowed us to keep track of how many NE superficial mentions were *noisy*, namely impacted by OCR errors.

B.2.2. Named Entity Classification (NEC)

B.2.2.1. General guidelines

- The types were assigned according to the AMR annotation guidance instructions¹ and selected from the AMR named entity types list². Sticking to the AMR annotation guidance instructions, the annotators were instructed to select the most specific type possible.

¹<https://www.isi.edu/~ulf/amr/lib/popup/ne-type-selection.html>

²<https://www.isi.edu/~ulf/amr/lib/ne-types.html>

B.2.2.2. Example in the Annotation Tool

- In the Annotation Tool, if the NE type predicted by SPRING [26] and BLINK [14] was wrong, the annotator could choose the correct type from a drop-down list.

B.2.3. Entity Linking (EL)

B.2.3.1. General guidelines

Figure B.3: EL - General guidelines

- The annotators were instructed to link the named entities recognized to their corresponding Wikidata ID (QID). In Figure B.3, we can see the slide used to support these general guidelines for the annotators.
- The annotators were instructed to assign a QID only if the context of the annotated sentence was sufficient for a human reader to disambiguate the entity. The annotators were instructed to annotate the named entity recognized with the string NIL if the context was insufficient.
- The annotators were instructed to assign the string NIL also to named entities not present in Wikidata.

B.2.3.2. Example in the Annotation Tool

- As we can see in Figure B.4, the annotator can assess whether the EL performed off-the-shelf by BLINK [14], the entity linker employed in the text2AMR parser [26] included in our [13, Text2AMR2FRED] module is correct or not. If it is incorrect, (as in the case of the Figure), the annotator is requested to record the correct Wikipedia page link and Wikidata QID.

B.2.4. Missing Named Entities

B.2.4.1. General guidelines

- The annotators were instructed to carefully scrutinize each sentence to ensure that no named entities were entirely overlooked by the by BLINK [14], the entity linker employed in the text2AMR parser [26] included in the [13, Text2AMR2FRED] tool.

Sentence #104 (BLEURT: 1) **The_Musical_World_ms_1843-042_3_**

The rest of the concert was made up of an exhibition on the violoncello, during which the "veteran" delighted us with "Polly put the kettle on"—some sentimentalities by Bellini, Pacini and Zingarelli, and the worn out terzetto from Il Matrimonio Segreto, which by this time I am quite tired of, though Miss Marshall, Mrs. Shaw and Mrs. Bushe did it ample justice, as far as singing went—I say nothing about acting.

Reset

Entity mention: **Mrs. Shaw**

This is Correct Wrong

Entity type: **person**

This is Correct Wrong

Wikipedia: [Mary_Shaw_\(actress\)](#)

This is Correct Wrong

Wikipedia page (if it exists)

Wikidata QID: [Q3850504](#)

This is Correct Wrong

Wikidata QID (if it exists)

Figure B.4: EL - Example in the Annotation Tool

B.2.4.2. Example in the Annotation Tool

- If any NEs were missed, annotators were directed to record them in the appropriate tab of the Annotations Tool, as in the example reported in Figure B.5.

Sentence #49 (BLEURT: 1) Dwight's Journal of Music_1855-002_ms_3

Below **Schandau** you pass the bold promontory of Schramstein, close sunder the fortified heights of Pfaffenstein, and 'Konigstein with its impregnable fortress—against whose walls Napoleon battered: in vain—thence on, through a wild country of tale-telling tradition, "thé cradle of gnomes and kobolds," till, at length, near Dresden you emerge among thriving . Villages and cultivated fields; like the exit, on the Neckar, from the vallies of Odenwald upon the plains of the Rhine at Heidelberg.

Missing named entities

Report the name of any named entity that you think is present in the text but is missing in the AMR graph

Leave the corresponding field(s) empty to remove an entity; empty fields are ignored

Entity name or mention (without OCR errors)

Entity name or mention (with OCR errors, if relevant)

Entity type

Wikipedia page (if it exists)

Wikidata QID (if it exists)

Figure B.5: Missing Named Entities - Example in the Annotation Tool

C. Appendix C

In this appendix, we report examples of the prompts experimented in sub-section 3.4.2.

C.1. Evidence span-augmented prompts

C.1.1. Example

Give the shortest and most informative possible answer to the following question: *How long was Teresina Brambilla's career as a musician?* considering the information contained in the following text span: *Teresa "Teresina" Brambilla (15 April 1845 – 1 July 1921) was an Italian soprano who sang in the major opera houses of Europe in a career spanning 25 years.*

C.2. AMR graph-augmented prompts

C.2.1. Prompt Example

Act as an expert in Abstract Meaning Representation. Give the shortest and most informative possible answer to the following question: *How long was Teresina Brambilla's career as a musician?* considering the information contained in the following Abstract Meaning Representation (AMR) graph:

```
(z0 / soprano
  :domain (z1 / person
    :wiki "Teresa_Teresina"
    :name (z2 / name
      :op1 "Teresa"
      :op2 "Teresina"
      :op3 "Brambilla")
    :time (z3 / date-interval
      :op1 (z4 / date-entity
        :day 15
        :month 4
        :year 1845)
      :op2 (z5 / date-entity
        :day 1
        :month 7
        :year 1921)))
  :mod (z6 / country
    :wiki "Italy"
    :name (z7 / name
      :op1 "Italy"))
  :ARG0-of (z8 / sing-01
    :location (z9 / house
      :ARG1-of (z10 / major-02)
      :mod (z11 / opera)
      :location (z12 / continent
```

```

:wiki "Europe"
:name (z13 / name
      :op1 "Europe"))
:duration (z14 / career
          :duration (z15 / temporal-quantity
                    :quant 25
                    :unit (z16 / year))))

```

C.3. RDF/OWL Knowledge Graph-augmented prompts

C.3.1. Prompt Example

Act as an expert in RDF/OWL Knowledge Graphs. Give the shortest and most informative possible answer to the following question: *How long was Teresina Brambilla's career as a musician?* considering the information contained in the following RDF/OWL Knowledge Graph:

```

<Soprano> <equivalentClass> <synset-soprano-noun-1> .
<date-interval_1> <hasMember> <date-entity_1> .
<synset-house-noun-4> <gloss> "the audience gathered together in a theatre or cinema; \
the house applauded\"; \he counted the house\\""@en-us .
<House> <equivalentClass> <synset-house-noun-4> .
<Europe> <sameAs> <Q46> .
<Europe> <sameAs> <Europe> .
<OperaHouse> <subClassOf> <House> .
<career_1> <for> <temporal-quantity_1> .
<Italy> <sameAs> <Q38> .
<Opera> <subClassOf> <InformationEntity> .
<Soprano> <hasQuality> <Italy> .
<synset-career-noun-2> <gloss> "the general progression of your working or professional
life; \the general had had a distinguished career\"; \he had a long career in the
law\\""@en-us .
<Year> <subClassOf> <TimeInterval> .
<Year> <subClassOf> <supersense-noun_time> .
<Europe> <type> <Continent> .
<date-entity_2> <type> <Date-entity> .
<major_1> <type> <major-02> .
<Italy> <sameAs> <Italy> .
<OperaHouse> <associatedWith> <Opera> .
<sing_1> <subsumedUnder> <Communication_manner> .
<date-entity_1> <day> "15"^^<decimal> .
<major-02> <label> "great in scope, extent, importance, etc" .
<temporal-quantity_1> <type> <Temporal-quantity> .
<date-entity_1> <type> <Date-entity> .
<sing_1> <singer> <Soprano> .
<sing_1> <for> <career_1> .
<synset-opera-noun-1> <gloss> "a drama set to music; consists of singing with orchestral
accompaniment and an orchestral overture and interludes"@en-us .
<house_1> <Location> <Europe> .
<temporal-quantity_1> <hasDataValue> "25"^^<decimal> .
<Italy> <type> <Country> .
<date-entity_2> <month> "7"^^<decimal> .
<date-interval_1> <type> <Date-interval> .
<sing_1> <subsumedUnder> <0347f> .

```

```

<Soprano> <subClassOf> <supersense-noun_person> .
<date-entity_1> <month> "4"^^<decimal> .
<sing-01> <subClassOf> <Event> .
<Teresa_Teresina_Brambilla> <type> <Person> .
<temporal-quantity_1> <hasQuantifier> <multiple> .
<career_1> <type> <Career> .
<sing-01> <label> "sing, performing vocal music" .
<Soprano> <subClassOf> <Person> .
<synset-year-noun-1> <gloss> "a period of time containing 365 (or 366) days; \"she is 4
  years old\"; \"in the year 1920\""@en-us .
<synset-soprano-noun-1> <gloss> "a female singer"@en-us .
<major_1> <subsumedUnder> <Importance> .
<date-interval_1> <hasMember> <date-entity_2> .
<sing_1> <type> <sing-01> .
<date-entity_2> <day> "1"^^<decimal> .
<Opera> <equivalentClass> <synset-opera-noun-1> .
<House> <subClassOf> <Collection> .
<Career> <equivalentClass> <synset-career-noun-2> .
<sing_1> <Location> <house_1> .
<Teresa_Teresina_Brambilla> <type> <Soprano> .
<Teresa_Teresina_Brambilla> <Time> <date-interval_1> .
<House> <subClassOf> <supersense-noun_group> .
<major_1> <great> <house_1> .
<Opera> <subClassOf> <supersense-noun_communication> .
<year_1> <type> <Year> .
<date-entity_1> <year> "1845"^^<decimal> .
<major-02> <subClassOf> <Event> .
<Year> <equivalentClass> <synset-year-noun-1> .
<Teresa_Teresina_Brambilla> <sameAs> <Teresa_Teresina> .
<house_1> <type> <OperaHouse> .
<Career> <subClassOf> <Situation> .
<date-entity_2> <year> "1921"^^<decimal> .
<temporal-quantity_1> <unit> <year_1> .
<Career> <subClassOf> <supersense-noun_act> .

```